

POPREBEL

**Populist rebellion against modernity in 21st-century
Eastern Europe: neo-traditionalism and neo-feudalism**

Working Paper no. 13

**Ethnography of uncertainty: Polish and Czech social
perception of populist upheaval, late pandemic and a
military conflict in Europe**

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POPREBEL (Populist rebellion against modernity in 21st-century Eastern Europe: neo traditionalism and neo-feudalism) is a large Horizon 2020-funded research project on the rise of populism in Central and Eastern Europe. The aim of the project is to describe the phenomenon, create a typology of its various manifestations, reconstruct trajectories of its growth and decline, investigate its causes, interpret its meanings, diagnose its consequences and propose policy solutions.

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The POPREBEL consortium comprises six universities – UCL (co-ordinating institution), University of Belgrade, Charles University, Corvinus University of Budapest, Jagiellonian University and University of Tartu – and Edgeryders, a social enterprise.

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Ethnography of uncertainty

Polish and Czech social perception of populist upheaval, late pandemic and a military conflict in Europe [D2.9]

Magdalena Góralaska and Jitka Králová

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1. Introduction

The analysis presented in this report aims to show how the Russian invasion of Ukraine and its consequences are construed by the participants of the ethnographic segment of the POPREBEL project. The analysis is set up against the background of people's views on other matters, examined extensively in an earlier, open-access report, 'A large-scale ethnography of populism in the Czech Republic, Germany and Poland' (Davidov *et al* 2022). Both stages of our ethnographic work were conducted mostly online among what we called *networked publics*. Our goal was the reconstruction of key building blocks people use in their construals of reality, construals that affect their (changing) political choices and their voting behaviour in the context of the Covid-19 crisis.

This report provides insight into interviews collected after Russia invaded Ukraine on February 24th 2022. The series of unprecedented events and dramatic changes which the war set in motion in the entire CEE region forced us to refocus our research. We had to assume that an event of such magnitude influences the perceptions, views, and future plans of the study's participants. We decided to carry on with the study, but create a separate dataset of interviews collected after the beginning of the war, where we also ask about the conflict. We were able to get a unique, first-hand insight into the perspectives and political implications of the conflict as perceived by the representatives of the Czech and Polish networked publics.

2. The fieldwork and methodology

The analysis presented in this report is based on a total of 40 interviews, collected via digital ethnography, which commenced on the day of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24th 2022, and ended on the 30th of September 2022. In a similar vein as the earlier dataset (Davidov *et al* 2022), the digital fieldwork was set across public online spaces where Czech and Polish 'netizens' express their views. Due to the popularity of Facebook across a variety of social groups in both societies, we chose to focus our attention on that platform. We followed the discussions and interactions taking place under articles about the war in Ukraine, informing about the conflict, including the international and domestic responses to it, posted by various media outlets in Poland and Czechia to their Facebook pages. Among those active with the posts we sought potential research participants. If their comment was expressing an opinion on the war, we would contact them with a private Facebook message explaining the purpose of the research, how we came across their Facebook profile (referencing the specific discussion under which they had commented) and asking whether they would be interested in taking part in the study.

If a person expressed interest, we would arrange an interview via an online call on the platform of participants' choice (either Facebook messenger call or Zoom), or if the participant felt uncomfortable speaking over a video or an audio call, we would offer them to carry out the interview in a written form via Facebook messenger chat ('chatnography'). Prior to the interview, each research participant would receive an information leaflet about the study and an electronic consent form to be signed before the beginning of the interview. Both were translated from English to either Czech or Polish. When it comes to methodological difficulties, the biggest limitation was posed by the technical setup of Facebook messenger, where

messages sent by users outside of one's friends' list are automatically redirected into the 'message requests', of which users are not automatically notified (unless they have the latest messenger version downloaded on their mobile phones). This significantly impacted the number of reachable participants and required large amounts of effort just to contact as many Facebook users as possible. We were able to interview over 70 people, and have selected the first 40 interviews, 20 for each country, to analyse in this short report. Each interview lasted on average about 40 minutes.

Research questions and questionnaire

In order to address the two key research questions at the core of the POPREBEL project, namely **how the ongoing global crises affect people's political choices and voting behaviour, and whether they give rise to new populist sentiments**, we organised interviews around five main topics:

1. General views about the ongoing war in Ukraine.
2. Perceptions of the government's approach to the conflict.
3. Experiences of the ongoing economic crisis (energy costs and inflation), and the government's response to it.
4. Perceptions of the current political representation and participant's general political views.
5. Brief commentary on the lived experience of the Covid-19 pandemic and the socioeconomic impacts of the restrictions.

These core thematic categories were discussed consistently with all the participants, while individual questions varied slightly depending on the participants' responses and interests. In detail, we asked participants about the following matters:

- **the conflict in Ukraine**, its implications for the global geopolitical order and for domestic security, the relationship to Russia,
- **the matter of Ukrainian refugees**, asking the study's participants whether they were in support or against the governmental approach to take in and accommodate thousands of Ukrainian refugees, inquiring about the value of solidarity with people escaping conflict, and drawing parallels with 2015 'refugee crisis' in the South of Europe, or the refugee crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border, ongoing since since 07.07.2021,
- **the experience of the Covid-19 pandemic**, the socioeconomic impacts of the restrictions on one's life, overall perception of the pandemic and the restrictions, attitude towards vaccination, reasons behind it, and so on,
- **the perceptions of the current government and its response to various crises**, were they content with the ruling coalition/why, how effectively do/did they address the pandemic crisis, the ongoing economic crises or the Ukrainian crisis,
- **the general state of politics**, how do they feel about the choice of political parties, who do they support/why, did the Covid-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine change their electoral choices, and why,
- **the state institutions**, can they rely on the help from the state if needed, should the state be helping, why/why not, what are some of the biggest gaps in the functioning of the state, what should be improved and what are some of the biggest challenges in the future,

- **the media**, overall perception of the mainstream media channels, how do they keep themselves up to date, can the media be trusted, and what do they think about disinformation,
- **the perception of the EU**, how they perceive the institution as a whole, and whether they see the benefits of EU membership.

In the following two sections we provide a general overview of the study's participants. We prepared two tables to provide a summary of their views on particular issues, in addition to basic demographic information. As people's perceptions are inherently ambivalent and nuanced, the tables provide only the basic overview of their view and show the composition of both samples. To differentiate the stance of research participants on three key issues, we initially categorise their views in binary terms: (1) *Pro/Anti Ukraine binary* captures participants' views on the governmental support for Ukraine in the war (including military aid and acceptance of refugees); (2) *Pro/Anti Covid binary* is designed to capture the attitude towards the mainstream explanation of the Covid-19 pandemic and its restrictions; (3) *Pro/Anti EU binary shows the essence of people's view of the EU and the country's membership in it*. Such classifications are an approximation of participants' political positions, and the views of our participants should not be perceived as falling into clear binary categories. To complexify the picture we begin by noting down inconsistencies and indecisive stands, and providing additional marking. In the tables, we use the sign ^ to represent inconsistencies. For example, if a participant agreed with the military support for Ukraine while simultaneously disagreeing with the welcome policy for Ukrainian refugees, we would use Ukraine: PRO^. We used either +/- signs in bold to indicate indecisive positions, nevertheless leaning more towards positive or negative views (in the used example, the participant would be therefore leaning towards pro).

It goes without saying that the participants' opinions were far from uniform, and their agreement/disagreement was expressed with varying levels and intensities. We tried to capture such complexities in the narrative part of the report.

2.1 Polish fieldwork

In both countries we sought interviewees amongst the followers of Facebook pages. In the Polish case we focused on the pages created by the key Polish media outlets, across the political left-right spectrum - DoRzeczy, Rzeczpospolita, Gazeta Wyborcza, and OKO.press. We have also focused on articles and commentary expressing reactions to the published views of political elites, including the government and opposition parties. Out of the 20 research participants of this sample, 10 identified as female (f) and 10 as male (m). Based on information shared with us, we estimate their political leanings as follows:

1. **right-wing, conservative, 2:** mostly interested in social-welfare, conservative moral values, state-interventionist (social-democratic) approach to economy, PiS voters, family oriented.
2. **centrist, liberal, 3:** mostly interested in the defeat of the Law and Justice party and expressing liberal moral values and a neoliberal approach to economy,
3. **centrist, conservative, 2:** mostly interested in the defeat of Law and Justice , conservative moral values, and a neoliberal approach to economy,
4. **leftist, liberal, 5:** mostly interested in moral issues, strong anti-Law and Justice party sentiment, liberal moral values, and a light neoliberal approach to the economy,

5. **leftist, social-democratic, 8:** mostly interested in social-welfare, liberal moral values, and the state-interventionist (social-democratic) approach to the economy.

We conducted interviews with twenty participants; they are briefly presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Polish participants in the study.

Username	F/ M	Town	Pro/Anti Ukraine	Pro/Anti Covid	Pro/Anti EU	Political leaning	Last voted for
PL60Ania30b	F	Rzeszów (183 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL61Irena70a	F	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(C) conservative	PO
PL62Michał40a	M	Rzeszów (183 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) liberal	Kukiz/Ra zem
PL63Gabriel20a	M	Gdańsk (582 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem/ Wiosna
PL64Arkadiusz50b	M	Bydgoszcz (354 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(C) conservative	Polska 2050
PL65Joachim30a	M	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL66Grzegorz20b	M	Bydgoszcz (354 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) liberal	PO/ SLD
PL67Mania30a	F	Suwałki (69 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL68Tadek30a	M	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL69Jurek30a	M	N/A	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) liberal	PO
PL70Władzio20a	M	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL71Hania60b	F	Kielce (196 000)	PRO [^]	PRO	ANTI	(R) conservative	PiS
PL72Klaudia50a	F	Nowy Dwór Mazowiecki (42 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(C) liberal	PO
PL73Jozefina30a	F	N/A	N/A	PRO	PRO	(C) liberal	PO
PL74Kazimierz60a	M	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(C) liberal	PO
PL75Kamila30b	F	Warsaw (1 765 000)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) liberal	PO/Raz em
PL76Mira20b	F	N/A	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) liberal	anti-PiS

PL77Matylda20a	F	N/A	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Razem
PL78Roza50b	F	Bydgoszcz (354 000)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(R) conservative	PiS
PL79Sebastian40b	M	Big city	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) social-dem	Lewica

Among the study participants, half are below the age of 35. The majority admit to having left-leaning political views, while conservative political views were noted amongst participants above the age of 50. The 50-50 gender balance is kept throughout different age categories. When it comes to the regional distribution, based on the information shared with us, 6 study participants currently reside in the capital city, 5 in cities with the number of inhabitants above 300,000, and 5 in cities and towns inhabited by 200,000 or less. When it comes to voting preferences, 7 study participants declared to have voted for PO, the Civic Platform party, and among those one has expressed centrist conservative views, 3 centrist-liberal, and 3 leftist-liberal. Among interviewees with conservative views, two have voted for the ruling Law and Justice party and two support centrist oppositional parties, PO and Polska2050.

2.2 Czech fieldwork

During the Czech part of the study, we were seeking interviewees among the followers of Facebook pages of some of the key Czech media outlets across the political left-right spectrum - ČT24, Seznam zprávy, Echo24, and A2LARM. We focused particularly on articles and commentary addressing the responses of the Czech government, run by the right-wing liberal coalition SPOLU.

Among the 20 interviews analysed in this report, 10 were conducted with male research participants and 10 with female ones. When it comes to the political leanings, we have classified them into six key categories, based entirely on the participants' personal accounts. As it was emphasised earlier, assigning people's views into specific categories is only approximate due to their complexity. The six categories are:

1. **right-wing, libertarian 4:** libertarian approach to economy (laissez-faire), light conservative moral values, against covid restrictions
2. **right-wing, conservative 4:** state-interventionist approach to economy, more towards national socialism, strong conservative moral values, SPD voters
3. **right-wing, liberal 2:** neoliberal approach to economy (little state intervention), liberal values (democracy, generally pro-Western orientation)
4. **centre-right, liberal 2:** neoliberal approach to economy (some limited state intervention), liberal values (democracy, pro-Western orientation, support of the EU)
5. **centre-left, progressive 2:** neoliberal approach to economy but more moderate state interventionist and redistributive policies, progressive left leaning values (social justice, equality, human rights)
6. **leftist, progressive 3:** critique of the neoliberal approach to economy, pro strong state interventionist redistributive policies, progressive left leaning values (social justice, equality, human rights)
7. **leftist, conservative 3:** extreme state-interventionist approach to economy (nationalisation), mostly interested in social-welfare, conservative moral values, nostalgia for the socialist regime

The table below presents the overview of the Czech study participants, with whom the conversations are analysed in this report.

Table 2: Czech participants in the study.

Username	F/M	Town (size)	Pro/Anti Ukraine	Pro/Anti Covid	Pro/An ti EU	Political leaning	Last voted for
0322lukas40b	M	Germany	PRO [^]	ANTI	ANTI	(R) libertarian	Trikolora
0322premysl50a	M	Zlin (75 thousand)	PRO [^]	ANTI	+/-	(L) conservative	Slachta
0322vilem60b	M	Kladno (69 thousand)	ANTI [^]	ANTI	PRO	(CL) progressive	Pirati
0322ludmila50a	F	Prague (1.3 mil)	ANTI [^]	ANTI	+/-	(R) libertarian	Svobodni
0322pavlina50b	F	Brno (380 thousand)	ANTI [^]	ANTI [^]	ANTI	(R) conservative	SPD
0422honza30a	M	Olomouc (100 thous)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(R) conservative	SPD
0422martina30a	F	Plzen (171 thous)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(R) conservative	SPD
0422leila30a	F	Havirov (69 thousand)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(R) liberal	SPOLU
0422rosta30a	M	Havirov (69 thousand)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(CR) liberal	STAN
0422vasek40b	M	Prague(1.3 mil)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(CR) liberal	SPOLU
0422monika50b	F	Prague(1.3 mil)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(R) liberal	SPOLU
0522bronislav50b	M	Prostejov (43,7 thous)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(L) conservative	Slachta
0522angelika50b	F	Dvur Kralove (15,7 thous)	ANTI [^]	ANTI	ANTI	(R) libertarian	Trikolora
0522bohuna50b	F	Kyjov (11,000)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(R) libertarian / conservative	Trikolora
0522laura30b	F	Germany	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) progressive	Zeleni
0522max30a	M	Prague (1,3 mil)	PRO	PRO	PRO [^]	(L) progressive	n/a
0522david20b	M	Prague (1,3 mil)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(CL) progressive	Pirati

0522milos50b	M	Usti n Labem (92 thousand)	PRO	PRO	PRO	(L) progressive	n/a
0522alena50a	F	Usti n Labem (92 thousand)	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(R) libertarian/ conservative	SPD
0622martina60b	F	n/a	ANTI	ANTI	ANTI	(L) conservative	SPD

3. The Polish case

In the weeks, or even days prior to the attack, Polish public opinion was unsure whether Putin is going to invade Ukraine (wPolityce.pl, 2022; PolsatNews.pl, 2022). A steep escalation of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict seemed just too unlikely. No one expected to receive the news of the war on Fat Thursday, a popular festivity that signals the upcoming Great Lent. On that day, as is customary, the entire Polish nation enjoys traditional sweet pastries, celebrating the end of the carnival season. To keep up with the enormous demand, bakeries work around the clock, starting the night before. So, on Thursday February 24th 2022, the bakers must have been one of the first to learn the terrifying news. In the early morning hours, when the Polish streets were feeling up with the aroma of freshly baked goods, Russia launched a cross country attack on Ukraine.

3.1 Context

3.1.1 Love thy neighbour? The popular mobilisation to aid Ukraine

Since the attack over 10 million people fled Ukraine through the Polish border (Ukrainianinpoland.pl, 2023). Around 2,7 million Ukrainians stayed in Poland, others continued their journey west, but over 8,3 millions eventually went back to help defend and rebuild their country (Pacewicz, 2023b). In a manner that fits well into the nation's glorified self-image, based, among others, on the legend of the Solidarity movement, Polish society has rushed to help its Ukrainian neighbour in a truly unprecedented manner. Poles have responded to the crisis swiftly and thoroughly, trying to help Ukrainians in every way imaginable. On the 24th February in a matter of hours hundreds gathered to protest in front of Russian diplomatic posts across the country, but thousands joined grassroots support initiatives that sprouted out of thin air in the following days.

Friends and strangers began organising through social media to pick up people at the border, arrange accommodation, food, and other basic goods, such as clothing, cosmetics or baby stuff, or serve as information centres, helping logistically. Many have donated to various Ukrainian NGOs, others started their own fundraisers with predefined goals, sponsoring high-tech field equipment for the Ukrainian army, medical supplies, or aiding evacuations of orphanages, dog shelters, or even entire villages.

Figure 1: Photo of Polish volunteers helping Ukrainians in the first days after war escalation, TVN24.pl, 27 February 2022, © TVN24

A study published by the Centre for Public Opinion Research (pol. *Centrum Badań Opinii Społecznej*, CBOS), shows broad societal support for the reception of Ukrainian refugees during the last year. It didn't fall below 80% for six months since February 24th, although it did decrease from the initial 94%, measured just after the escalation of the conflict (CBOS 2022a, 2022b). Such numbers are indeed truly exceptional, as the same study compared the 2022 results to data from previous years, noticing a sharp change of sentiment. Before the escalation Polish support for Ukrainian refugees wasn't nearly as high, as only a little over 50% of respondents would give an affirmative answer to a question whether or not Poland should welcome Ukrainian refugees from regions affected by the same war, since its outbreak in 2014. The sudden reality of full-scale war taking place in Europe raised fears about political and economic safety on a global scale, but particularly in countries geographically closest to the conflict. It seems that the war has had an unexpected positive effect on the Polish-Ukrainian relations, on the societal as well as on the political level.

Society's response has sent a clear message to the ruling coalition about what the majority of the public, including their own voting base, thinks and wants to happen. Although the government had no choice but to address both the societal as well as international concerns despite having previously a rather complicated relationship with Ukraine, it didn't react quickly and effectively enough to avoid broad criticism. The state-funded program for Ukrainians seeking refuge in Poland wasn't announced until spring (Dziennik Ustaw, 2022) nor were the promises of military aid met on time (Polityka.pl, 2022). The government eventually committed considerable resources, mitigated its earlier shortcomings, and Poland became one of Ukraine's key strategic allies, not only sharing its own resources but also advocating for foreign aid or lobbying for harsher sanctions on Russia. Yet, many critics accused the ruling coalition of using the situation to their own political advantage, by aiming to raise the country's international standing, particularly within the EU. According to the most common criticism, the government appropriated largely autonomous popular mobilisation to aid Ukrainians and used

it to improve its image, tarnished greatly by the simmering conflict with the EU over the Polish violations of the EU laws and norms concerning the independence of the judiciary, among other issues (Tilles 2022).

The neighbourly relationship between Poland and Ukraine has been long marked by the ambiguity that originates in complex regional history, as well as in more recent political tensions. The latter oscillates mostly around two topics: (1) opening the job market to Ukrainians, and (2) divergent interpretations of various historical events that have defined modern Polish-Ukrainian relations.

3.1.2 The political significance of Polish-Ukrainian historical animosities

To understand why it wasn't obvious that the Polish would help Ukrainians the way they did, we must understand the state of collective memory in both countries, as it is always a potential source of political tensions between the neighbours. The societies living in the region, as well as the political elites ruling them, have been tightly bound throughout the whirlwind of history that has made their relationship quite complicated, starting with the semi-legendary origins of both countries in the Middle Ages. While there is definitely no doubt that the foreign power that played the biggest role in modern Ukrainian history is Russia, it is Poland that has claimed the role centuries prior. Before the mid-17th century, when the Russian Empire gained long-lasting influence in the region, it was the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth that held Kievan Rus' subordinate. The principality of Kievan Rus, which is seen today as a predecessor of modern-day Ukraine, was under the strong cultural influence of the Polish Crown. Its Catholicisation politics resulted in a gradual Polonisation of the local nobility and their subordinates, laying the groundwork for any and all future Polish claims to lands, which today are part of Ukrainian territory.

When the Russian Empire ceased to exist in the aftermath of the First World War and the Bolshevik revolution, hopes of the Ukrainian nationalist movement to create an independent statehood were eventually crushed by the Bolsheviks and their new policy on nationalities, but also by the actions of the newly established Second Republic of Poland. The new political entity incorporated Western Ukrainian provinces¹, and went on with its broad Polonisation campaign. Ukrainian nationalists in these provinces actively resisted Polonisation, sometimes resorting to violence through minor acts of terrorism. The campaign resulted in the intensification of ethnic tensions between Poles and Ukrainians (Hrycak 2000, Portnov 2020). Growing anti-Polish sentiment among members of the Ukrainian minority eventually led to severe bloodshed in the wake of World War Two, which continued throughout the war and onto the post-war period. Various groups didn't accept the new status quo and continued to resist the new border layout.

After WWII, to suppress strong ethnic tension in the borderline region with Ukrainian SSR, Polish People's Republic and the Soviet Union introduced forced resettlement policies. As a result, tens of thousands of Poles have been repatriated from the "Kresy" region to the lands belonging to pre-war Germany, while members of other ethnic groups, especially those

¹ The rest of what we know today as Ukraine was partitioned between the USSR, Romania, and Czechoslovakia.

suspected of separatism, were scattered across more Polish regions. While the forced relocation policies succeeded in bringing ethnic tensions to an end, they also helped the communist governments with another of their major goals - ethnic homogenization. A homogeneous society was seen as the necessary foundation for ensuring a stable state, a stable economy and prosperity for all in a society without any social divisions. It is not surprising, as communist governments, despite their rhetorics praising internationalism, were often quite nationalistic (or imperialist, in the case of the USSR) (Verdery 1991).

Nonetheless, the Polish-Ukrainian relationships were increasingly warming up, despite historical animosities, following a new political agenda that aimed to “clear the air” with both sides openly admitting to their countries’ past wrongdoings. In the 1990s, after the fall of the Soviet Bloc, consecutive Polish governments, supported by academics and public intellectuals, have openly condemned forced repatriation policies as forms of ethnic cleansing. When Ukraine was going through political turmoil in the early 2000s during the Orange Revolution, Poland expressed strong support for the initiative and its goal to weaken Russian influence in the country, eventually clearing its political scene from any pro-Russian sentiment. In 2014, when the Maidan protests happened and the Revolution of Dignity began (Woods 2014), the foreign policy of the Civic Platform coalition government (2010-2018) continued to provide political support to Ukraine’s democratic efforts. A 2017 study showed, for example, that in people’s views Ukrainians had been the target of hate speech in Poland less frequently than Jews or refugees from the Middle East and Sub-Saharan Africa (Hansen 2017:3-4).

As a result, two major sources of conflict, both regarding controversial historical events, the renovation of the Cemetery of the Defenders of Lwów (Rzeczpospolita, 2022) and the Wołyń/Volhynia massacre (Baczynska 2018) were recontextualised and the process of reconciliation over these tragic memories seems to have accelerated. The warming-up of the relationship had also a more practical rationale. Poland had to acknowledge a clear need for a migratory labour force that would replace millions of Poles who emigrated West, especially since Poland joined the EU in 2004. Ukraine wanted to join the Union, or at least strengthen its position within the EU, in hope of bettering its economic situation. Thanks in part to Poland’s political support, Ukrainians were added to the list of nations that can travel to EU countries visa-free (Jaroszewicz 2017).

Around the same time, some left-leaning Polish academic and civil society circles have begun to advocate for a new critical take on the history of Polish domination in the region (Radynski, 2014). A number of works have been published that define the feudal relationship between Polish nobility and Ukrainian (as well as Lithuanian or Belarusian) peasantry using terms offered by the post-colonial theory. Such a perspective not only allows us to see the history through the eyes of the poor majority, but also balances out the traditional and often state-supported historical discourses that tend to focus on military victories, dominant groups in the society, such as nobility, and glorify particular periods of Polish history. Such critical revisions are to an extent a response to some anti-Ukrainian narratives, coming mostly from conservative, right-wing circles, that continue to emphasise conflicts and tragedies of joint history to support their political agenda.

Specifically interpreted events drawn from two periods, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (1386/1569-1795) and the Second Republic of Poland (1918-39), have been used over the years by various conservative politicians to build othering narratives towards the Ukrainian

neighbour and nationalistic identity politics. Since its 2015 electoral victory, the Law and Justice coalition government and other public institutions controlled by it have started a number of initiatives aiming to pull out various historical figures from the depths of oblivion. Among others, significant funds were provided to help commemorate civilian self-defence and partisan Home Army units, which tried to protect Polish civilians in the Kresy region from ethnic cleansing massacres undertaken by Ukrainian nationalists. The move added to the tension between the two countries, as right-wing circles in Ukraine have also been using similar discursive tactics in their memory politics, presenting their interpretation of the history.

There is one particular chapter of history that has been consistently fueling discord and has had huge influence on how the two societies and their politicians think about each other. It is the extreme-right Ukrainian nationalist movement and the figure of its best known leader, Stepan Bandera, leader of the radical militant wing of the Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists (OUN-B), the Ukrainian Insurgent Army (UPA). The organisation, classified as fascist or fascist-like by some historians (Rossoliński-Liebe 2014, Rudling 2016:32) and as ultranationalist-liberationist by others (Zaitsev 2015), has been held responsible for the 1943-1944 massacres of Polish people residing in the disputed Volhynia and Eastern Lesser Poland regions (Motyka 2016). While the dominant discourse in Poland portrays him as a murderer, responsible for thousands of innocent deaths, in modern-day Ukraine Bandera is seen mostly as a war hero, who committed his life to serving the cause of Ukrainian independence. In 2010 he was posthumously awarded by Viktor Yushchenko, Ukraine's president at the time, with the title of the Hero of Ukraine, the highest distinction the president can award to an individual. The act was met with a broad critique across the world, starting with Ukrainians in the Eastern part of the country, Polish society and government, Jewish communities and organisations, and the EU, leading to Yushchenko revoking the award (Reuters 2010).

While only few conservative circles deny today that Wołyń massacre was indeed a genocide carried out by Ukrainian nationalists, Bandera continues to be praised across the country, though mostly in Western Ukraine (Kaniewski 2018, Tilles 2022). Polish historians have continued to argue that Ukrainian relativisation of historical figures downplays the severity of atrocities Bandera committed, ordered or inspired (Motyka 2016). The two previous Ukrainian governments (of Viktor Yanukovych and Petro Poroshenko) and the current government have made some efforts to reduce tension with Poland, but without igniting a significant change to the way Bandera is portrayed. Until recently.

The 2022 escalation of the Russian-Ukraine conflict has brought significant change in the neighbourly relationship between the two countries. With Poland becoming Ukraine's major ally in the EU, Zelenskyy's government made sure not to flaunt any Bandera references. While initially Poles were not able to shy away from jokes about the new Ukrainian president being an actor, today no one perceives him to be anything else but a hero.

While without doubt, the escalation of the war had an enormous impact on Polish-Ukrainian relations, both in the political and societal dimension, it might also have affected the Polish national self-image. Despite changing public opinions about the conflict and its regional impact, including the refugee crisis, the escalation in Russian aggression has brought out all the features that Poles stereotypically perceive as their national qualities, such as heroism, selflessness, bravery, or solidarity (Giza *et al*, 2013).

3.2 Analysis of the Ethnographic Data

Numerous acts of goodwill and broad participation in the joint societal effort to help Ukrainians have created a community of experience that seems to have turned the tide for Polish-Ukrainian relations. Despite the complicated joint history, strewn with animosities that are easy to politicise by mnemonic entrepreneurs on both sides, Poles responded with help. In the following paragraphs we present key topics and perspectives regarding the current Russo-Ukrainian conflict, that come from the interviews with Polish study participants. The first section provides insights into various narratives around the event itself, while the second section speaks about their approaches to Ukrainian refugees.

3.2.1 *The Conflict in Ukraine*

First days after the attack

The Russian attack is deeply ingrained in the memory of the study participants, irrespective of their political views. It was a “*shock, dread, and disbelief*” that “*a [real] war can be happening so close*” (PL77Matylda20a). Gabriel, a student of nursing, remembers:

I am telling you. I woke up that day, I remember it vividly, and immediately noticed a sea of notifications on my phone, that the war in Ukraine broke out. I was in total shock. I was stupefied. I thought, oh my God, the war is so close to us. What’s going to happen? What’s going to happen with the people in Ukraine? Will they get the help they need? (PL63Gabriel20a)

Some of the interviewees channelled their dismay into anger, attending anti-war manifestations that popped out in front of Russian diplomatic posts across the country when the news about the 24.02 attack broke out. When we asked Matylda, a student living in Warsaw, about what she and her friends did when they found out, she said: “*The first thing that I did was to join the protest in front of the Russian embassy in Warsaw. I know it really doesn’t do anything, but I wanted to feel good, feel like I am doing something*” (PL77Matylda20a). The study participants often recalled the sense of helplessness as the most dreadful sensation that accompanied them during the first couple of days, when various aid initiatives just started to take shape. Klaudia, who is over 50 years old and lives in a small town in the Mazovia region, shares:

In situations like that, the worst thing for me is sitting and doing nothing. And the conflict is so close. Our lives are here. But then the news quickly went out that mothers with children are running towards our border. So, when did it start, on Thursday or was it Wednesday? Anyway, on Saturday we were already there, in Medyka, helping out Ukrainians. (PL72Klaudia50a)

The proximity to Ukraine had some influence, whether it was a fact of generally living in Poland, or in the Eastern part of the country, closer to the warzone. Michał, who lives with his family in a large city close to the Ukrainian border, admitted he was expecting the worst:

Generally speaking, I really was under the impression that the New World Order is on the horizon, that the Russians will soon be a few kilometres from our Eastern border. It was a possibility. Maybe it has seemed as not very probable to someone, who doesn't follow politics, just follows the mainstream media. But not for me. (PL62Michal40a)

Ania, another study participant, shared how her child was watching the news about the war, and she had to explain what was happening. And was asked in response, "*mum, but why is Russia, the biggest country in the world, attacking another country? Don't they have enough?*" Ania comments, "*You know, that's the question exactly. A perfect summary of what's happening*" (PL60Ania30b).

Most of the interviewees didn't harbour any suspicious thoughts, with the exception of one interviewee, Hania, a retired polster and PiS voter. When the war broke out, she immediately thought about Russians that could secretly pass through the Polish border with the wave of Ukrainians, and try attacking Ukraine from the other side:

"I don't mean like with tanks, or anything, but... the Russians are just like that. My husband says it's their mentality, and it will never change. It's that they think they are the best, and at the same time, they can only exist [as a nation] when they are fighting for their homeland. They need to keep fighting for it. It's what unifies them, and makes it bearable to live under Putin's heel and in such conditions. Although I don't really know what the conditions are, I heard they have it way worse than we do". (PL71Hania60b)

While no one was supporting the Russian side, Ania, who belongs to a different generation and votes left, feels bad for the common Russian:

I am all in for Ukrainians. I wish for them... I was about to say, I wish they destroy the Russians, but I am not sure it's right to wish Russians to have their entire country fall apart. (PL60Ania30b)

Interestingly, most interviewees would talk about the war "breaking out", while the Russian attack on the 24th of February 2022 was in fact an escalation of the war, that began in 2014, with Russia's invasion of Crimea, Donbas and Luhansk regions, as recently confirmed by the European Council of Human Rights (Tropin, 2023). Irena, a retired journalist in her early 70s, says the event was what made her realise that "*we are sitting on a volcano*" and that the war "*is just a beginning of something bigger, although we don't know what yet*", "*but the feeling I have is that a huge explosion is on the horizon, the energy is such, it's like we're on a verge of a gigantic, dangerous disruption*", and that the Russian invasion of Ukraine is just the first step (PL61Irena70a).

Living with the war next door

While the first weeks were very tense, bringing a lot of turmoil to the lives of our interviewees, soon it became clear that the war might linger for quite some time. Mira, who has a corporate administrative job, shares: "*I was really worried the first week. I couldn't think about anything else, really. But with time... everyone somewhat got over with it, it became part of our everyday reality*" (PL76Mira20bUKR). She then adds:

However, a few days in, or after the first week, I learned that one of the girls who works with me in the company, and is Ukrainian, her mother is still in Mariupol, their hometown. It took 3 months to get her out of there, because of the shelling. And it really has stuck with me, although it doesn't touch me personally, it's not my family and neither is she my close friend. But every time I heard something on the TV or read online, I always thought of her and her mum, wondering whether she's okay. You see, there were weeks when my friend had no news from her mum, she couldn't get in touch with her at all. There was no phone connection, nothing. It was all really difficult. And still is. (PL76Mira20bUKR)

Another study participant, Klaudia, who got quickly involved in various aid initiatives, shares how the war is still with her every day. Although we spoke in the summer, she kept being engaged in helping Ukrainians:

You know, all that, it really did touch me. It still touches me. With some Ukrainian ladies, I have developed relationships. When they were going through things, I was by their side going through it with them. Wala, who was living with us for a while, she wanted to be up to date, to know what was happening but also knew it would be better if she could distance herself from it a bit, and have a break. She really was traumatised. But, in the end, she continued to watch the news. [...] So we were sitting on a couch together, watching the Ukrainian news, and crying. Eventually, I thought it was best that I don't get so emotionally involved. You see, I need to be there for them. I have to be the rock they can lean on, don't get caught up in all that... So I have survived, and I am still surviving through this conflict. (PL72Klaudia50a)

The study participants who had any personal relationship with Ukrainians, either developed before the war or because of it, contributed to their reaction to the escalation of the conflict, and their sense of worry.

With the war continuing, many interviewees eventually stopped following the news as closely as they did during the first couple of weeks. Michał, a programmer in his early 40 who lives close to the Ukrainian border, said that the one thing he learned from reading so much about the conflict, following various analysts and commentators, is that the war is also "*a media war, which Ukraine is winning, hence we cannot really trust anything that is being said by the media, as no real data is shared*" (PL62Michał40a). However, what goes without saying is the impact the war has on the economy. Władzio, who is an engineer in his early 20s, points out dreadfully:

We need to be aware, the war is impacting the housing market, the prices of literally everything, in a manner that's frankly quite shocking. If it's all going to continue down this path, the number of poor people will keep growing. The employers are not really up for the task when it comes to raising wages to make up for the inflation, that's eating up more and more of our income. It's the exact opposite, actually, they are looking for ways to save up, so they end up firing people. Both companies, big and small. That's what I keep hearing. (PL70Władzio20a)

Besides the whooping economic crisis that started with the pandemic, and got enhanced by the war, life in Poland hasn't changed that much. Somehow, the war next door became part

of the everyday, with people getting used to it, in various ways. Grzegorz, an IT specialist in his late 20s, admits that four months in, he is not that depressed with *“the drama that’s taking place in Ukraine”* anymore (PL66Grzegorz20b). However, while the initial shock is gone, and the fear of the Russians knocking on his door anytime has lessened, there are still *“rockets flying around across the border”*, and the war seems to be nowhere close to ending.

Response of the government

In most cases, our study participants described the reaction of the government and the ruling coalition as significantly different from the way the society at large responded. Our previous report (Davidov 2022) clearly shows that images of economic hardship and disappointment are firmly rooted in the Polish political culture, at least at the time of our study (2020-23). We hypothesise that this constitutes one of the reasons for the growing support of right-wing populism; this is confirmed by other studies (see, for example, Sadura and Sierakowski, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022). Similar critical sentiments were expressed when it comes to the state’s reaction to the recent escalation of the Russo-Ukrainian war.

The government’s response was seen as lacking and insufficient. Gabriel, a nursing student in his early 20s, remembers *“a real mess”*, and that *“the government failed to manage these activities for refugees well”*, as it wasn’t *“prepared for the scale”* (PL63Gabriel20aUKR). Tadek, a left-voter in his early 30ties, expands his critique of state response to the EU:

First of all, knowing that US intelligence informed all EU countries that the invasion would probably take place in February, I think that not only Poland, but all of Europe could have prepared much better. Poland, on the other hand, was the most involved in this matter, yet still, the first weeks or months could have been prepared much better. In the end, everything fell on the shoulders of ordinary volunteers, ordinary people. Poland as a nation stepped up more than the government as such (PL68Tadek30aUKR)

Many interviewees didn’t seem surprised by the state underdelivering in a crisis situation. Jurek, a journalist in his early 30s, points out that *“Poland is a country of go-fund-me”* (PL69Jurek30aUKR). This comment suggests that while the Polish can get together and unite over a shared cause, they do it to make up for the state’s shortcomings. What the government and the ruling coalition did was take advantage of what individuals and societal organisations did, and *“utilise it to grow their support in the polls”* while *“the government didn’t do much”* (PL66Grzegorz20bUKR). Grzegorz bitterly points out that the politicians *“are somewhat quite conscious of the threat the Russia poses and highlight how Russia is the main threat to us, our state, and the whole continent, but let’s see how this will translate onto reality”*. Kazimierz sums it up well by saying *“Poland is perceived as such a strong player because everyone is interested in what is happening here, but in fact, it is very weak. We are a weak country”* (PL74Kazimierz60aUKR:).

Another study participant has a different take on the government’s response. She hasn’t personally joined the popular mobilisation to aid Ukrainians but supports the effort. To Hania, a retired social polster and a PiS voter, the reaction of the government was adequate, because they *“made the decision to include Ukrainians living in Poland into some social benefit programmes, like 500 PLN plus for each child, or allow them to get jobs easily”*

(PL71Hania60b). Interestingly, another PiS voter, Róża, who works as a medical secretary in the State Sanitary Inspectorate, has a very different take on the same policy:

It's encouraging people to not work. Indeed, I do think the 500 plus is alright, but not when it comes to the Ukrainian children, the Ukrainians. We should have created refugee camps here in Poland for them, as it is usually done for refugees across the world. They should be controlled, so no mafia or other such things end up in Poland. And that's it. And the way it is, some secret agents and others can come in... (PL78Roza50b)

While the government eventually introduced state-level support to Ukrainian refugees [PRZYPIS], it seemed late and chaotic. Irena, a retired journalist who supports the opposition, honestly admitted that she *“even doesn't know what the government is doing”*, the information availability is so bad (PL61Irena70a).

Additionally, when it comes to what should have been improved, except revised crisis response strategies, the conflict escalation brought to the surface the need to improve the condition of the Polish army. Military investment is a constant in each of the Law and Justice election programs. Yet, the promise is labelled populist as PiS wasn't able to deliver it - *“it's hard for me to believe they [PiS] will be able to make our army bigger and keep the quality, our government is rather quite decrepit”* (PL66Grzegorz20bUKR).

The Ukrainians and Ukraine

When it comes to the way our interviewees perceive Ukrainians themselves, the narratives were mostly positive. This is supported by other studies. One of them shows that since the Russian invasion in February 2022, the respect and positive attitude towards Ukrainians only increased (Babińska *et al* 2022).

A PiS voter, Hania declares having *“a lot of kindness for them [Ukrainians]”* (PL71Hania60b). She is a retired pollster from a mid-sized town in central Poland and votes for the Law and Justice party because of their social policies. When the war escalated, she was really surprised and upset. Yet, *“when they defended themselves [against the Russians] I was so proud like I was me, myself, who defended Ukraine”*, adding *“I really admire [what they did]”* (PL71Hania60b). Another study participant in a similar age, Irena, a retired journalist, who remembers the early post-war years, says that Ukrainians were always so proactive:

The Ukrainians, who came to Poland throughout all those years, it turned out, are a bunch of people who just want to do something, help others at their own expense. [Those people], there's a gigantic potential, I can still feel it, and the war made it even more clear. (PL61Irena70a)

While Ukrainian bravery is being applauded, it is not romanticised or glorified. The war is a tragedy that destroys lives, and there is nothing beautiful about it. Klaudia, who has been actively helping many Ukrainians, including by offering them accommodation at her home, speaks about one of her guests:

Her grandson, who also lived with us, didn't leave the bed for a few days in a row, after they arrived. I thought to myself, good for him, he had to be brave and strong for so long, and he isn't even a teenager. All their family members were back there. (PLKlaudia50a)

Some research participants compare the way Ukrainians responded to the war with how Polish would act, or they themselves would. Michał admits to not believing Polish would have the same “*willpower, like the majority of men in Ukraine who stayed behind to defend their country*”, as he himself wouldn't go and fight: “*As a father, I have a child to provide for. I could totally work miles away from Poland and don't care, because of him*” (PL62Michal40a).

While the way Ukrainians responded to the war was praised by all our interviewees, they didn't necessarily change the way the nationality was perceived previously. Kazimierz, an art expert in his early 60, who teaches art history to students at a private university, thinks there are major differences between “us” and “them”:

At least half of my students are from Ukraine, Belarus and other places, the Polish are a minority. It's a very diverse group, and they all get along despite differences on a basic level like consumer behaviour, so to say. They dress the same, they frequent the same places, like the same movies. But on the level of skills and social characteristics, they are different. It's really striking, the way they lack general knowledge, it's a kind of illiteracy. (PL74Kazimierz60a)

After giving it some thought, he adds:

On the other hand, however, maybe it's true for the entire young generation. Yet, it's easier for them to have a stand on various social issues, like civil liberties or climate change. And in this regard I think Ukrainians or Belarusians are more libertarian, they value their freedoms more than Poles. (PL74Kazimierz60a)

Comparisons between the Polish and Ukrainians are rare and usually are in favour of the Ukrainians, particularly when it comes to the war or similar contexts, such as Belarusian nationwide protests in the summer of 2020. Openly negative comments on Ukrainians are very few and related to Ukrainian refugees (see the next section). It might be that study's participants feel like it's inappropriate to criticise the neighbouring nation, especially given the situation.

3.2.2 *The Ukrainian refugees*

Refugees welcome

The massive, grassroots mobilisation has sent a clear message that Ukrainian refugees are welcomed by Polish society. Even if not everyone directly engaged in helping, the broad support for Ukrainians was reflected in opinion polls, overshadowing any public critique of refugee aid for months to follow. Many of our interviewees have observed various ways the society has engaged in helping Ukrainians, or have themselves helped the refugees. Did their political views or voting choices influence their response to the crisis? How did it matter, if at all?

Study participants have expressed almost unanimously positive attitudes towards Ukrainian refugees. With one exception, irrespective of their political leanings, the interviewees agreed that Poland should be welcoming towards Ukrainians. For example, Matylda, a student in her early 20s who votes Left, engaged right away in helping, asking her Ukrainians friends what to do and how to best help. She eventually kept volunteering for about two months at the state-sponsored PTAK Center for Humanitarian Relief at the Warsaw EXPO fair and exhibition halls:

I was there May-June, and I was first sorting the clothes people were donating [...]. Next I could shift to the animal care centre, there were really a lot of people who arrived with their cats and dogs. In those huge halls there was plenty of space, we could accommodate many. There was everything there in the EXPO, a really great food sector, with a diverse offer, including sweets, and some entertainment, like a piano and toys for the kids, an entire kindergarten section, a sports section with basketball. (PL77Matylda20a)

While there was not much privacy in the halls and it was all set up quite provisionally, Matylda thinks the organisation at the EXPO relief centre was great and well addressed the first needs of incoming refugees. As of January 2023, the centre has helped a total of 75,000 refugees, with over 5000 refugees remaining at the facility.²

Another study participant, Klaudia, how is twice the age of Matylda and holds more centrally positioned political views, when she heard about the wave of Ukrainian refugees running away from the war to Poland, didn't think twice and immediately went to the Polish border with Ukraine *"taking them [by car] to nearby towns or means of mass transportation, giving them my number, just in case they needed help"* (PL72Klaudia50a). She became very active and so did other members of her family, also hosting refugees in their homes and helping them to settle in Poland or get to their final destination. Klaudia thinks that in Warsaw, the capital city where she resides, pretty much everyone somehow got involved. Another centre-sympathising study participant, Kamila rented her own apartment and moved to live with her parents, seeing the growing need for housing (PL75Kamila30bUKR).

While Matylda's and Klaudia's involvement pertained mostly to volunteer work in and around places where refugees were stationed, or otherwise directly helping refugees, others were helping through donations of foods, clothes, money or various tools and equipment. Jurek, a journalist who lives in the capital city and votes anti-PiS was amazed by the agitation and the social response, shares an example of the goodness he witnessed:

I am at a xerox point, about to pay, when this guy comes in and says that he needs photocopies quickly, and that he wants to pay with a card. And the place doesn't accept cards. He says he needs copies of documents for Ukrainians he is helping, and that he was driving all night, getting people from the border. So I say to the owner, don't give me my change back, use to pay for the 20 copies that guy needed. So there are the three of us, standing surrounded by xerox machines, three big blocks standing in silence and crying. That's how it was. It was one great emotion. (PL69Jurek30aUKR)

² <https://humanitarianexpo.com/>

Sometimes, the help would be just an act of everyday kindness in a very neighbourly manner. Hania, a retired pollster, votes for the Law and Justice Party, however, she isn't as conservative as the other PiS voter in our sample, Róża. Hania isn't Catholic, she declares herself to be a Buddhist. She and her husband live in a small town in the central part of Poland, and are generally very critical of Polish political culture and distrustful towards media news coverage. In the neighbourhood where she lives, there is a hotel, which was turned into an accommodation centre for Ukrainian refugees. She was delighted that it happened, having nothing critical to say about it:

I sometimes meet Ukrainians, in that hotel that's a block down from where I live. I am not sure what are the rules, who pays for it, but that's it. Their children are attending the school nearby. In the beginning, their mothers would get lost, and couldn't find the school building, so I would ask them sometimes if they needed any help, and I would show them where the school was. You see, there's this shortcut from the hotel to the school, but those maps in the phone do not see it. I really have a lot of kindness towards them, really.

In over all, the way our interviewees spoke about Ukrainian refugees underlined their bravery and their fighting spirit:

The attitudes I came across, I really admire. The women [that I helped], who were surely quite traumatised with all the running from the war, family left behind or separated... Still they would go out of the house with this dignity, saying they want to work, want to help me, as they don't want to be living on someone's charity. (PL72Klaudia50a)

Many did however say they heard some negative remarks on the refugee behaviour, for example gossip on refugees stealing from someone (PL72Klaudia50a). She also heard some people complaining that "*they will take the job from us*" or that "*Ukrainians think they can have everything for free*", although of course "*there are different people in each nation, so maybe that's why people have different experiences and judge Ukrainians differently, but I cannot say that I do*" (PL72Klaudia50a). Hania also heard such stories, including a critique of a Ukrainian guy "*who didn't go back to to fight for his country at all, but instead got his family to come here, got an apartment and now lives here*" (PL71Hania60b). She doesn't comment what she thinks about it, but she sees Ukrainian refugees for whom they are - normal people, not very different from her own nation, having similar troubles, good and bad people who have different priorities.

Another PiS voter, Roza was a notable exception in the sample (PL78Roza50bUKR) who declared herself as a radical conservative and showed strong distrust, suggesting that among the Ukrainians arriving in Poland there might be members of mafia, spies and that the best way to protect us from such threats would be to create refugee camps like other countries had purportedly done:

the 500+ [childcare support program] p is ok [for Polish], but not for Ukrainian children, not for the Ukrainian nation... They should be set up in refugee camps, as is usually the case in the world, they should be controlled so that mafias and other things do not come to Poland. And that's it. And this is how they can come out on some... undercover agents and others... (PL78Roza50bUKR)

Grzegorz, an IT specialist in his late twenties, points out that Poles have rushed, in various ways, to help Ukrainian refugees. He has mostly positive views on how the society have responded to the crisis, but muses that “*they were so helpful, in an individual capacity, it was a form of self-fulfilment, a way to ease one’s own mind*” against the atrocity of war next door (PL66Grzegorz20bUKR).

Proud to be Polish, but...

When asked about how Polish society has responded to the crisis, study participants mostly saw it as something very positive, right, something to be proud of. Kamila, an architect from a large city in central Poland, who votes centre-left, noticed that there “*is a bit of a narrative among my friends that they are no longer ashamed of being Polish*” (PL75Kamila30bUKR). Irena, a retired journalist in her early 70s, shares:

I remember how it was at the beginning [after the escalation], I had an impression, I really was really built with the social reaction. It turned out there are so many people in Poland, who are ready to act, to do something, that energy that was suppressed before was released. Suddenly, it turns out we, as a nation, are not indifferent, it’s not true, what they say is that we don’t care. [...] Turns out that we are able to do great things, actually go and help people in need, with an authentic aim of caregiving, of sharing whatever they can, their flats, beds, money... (PL61Irena70a)

People we spoke to saw it as a total experience - something that has unified the nation against all differences, and in particular, against political divides. The reaction to the war in Ukraine was grand and needed, with Poles living up to their legendary self-stereotype of being always ready to engage in a popular uprising (pol. *pospolite ruszenie*). This has happened, some people noted, occasionally throughout history, with the most recent example being the Solidarity movement of the 1980s. This reaction was, however, quite unexpected. Many of our interviewees expressed the surprise:

There is usually a very low level of such civic behaviour [among Poles]. If there is a flood, they help, if there is a war, they will do something, they help Ukraine. But in everyday life they are fed up, and don’t care about situations that do not directly concern them. It is related to the communist heritage, which I think, were such an approach that someone should only deal with their own issues, nothing more, it’s the smartest way to be (PL74Kazimierz60aUKR)

When the war escalated, the bottom-up, social response was the quickest, but the scale of required assistance was beyond anybody’s imagination and certainly above anything people were prepared for. The scale of the refugee influx and lack of preparation raised worries of short-lived enthusiasm for helping:

We, as a Polish society, have a flash in the pan approach to many of our undertakings. In the first weeks after all those humanitarian actions, initiatives, it really was a lot. I didn’t expect the conflict to stop after a month, but I think people have just moved on, and got used to the idea of the war next door. And the strain of the sheer number of Ukrainians who made it to Poland, and stayed. I don’t think Poles were mentally

prepared for it, for how long this war can last. I think many people are just tired now. (PL76Mira20b)

While Mira is glad Polish have quickly responded to the crisis, similarly to Kazimierz she observes that the initial enthusiasm to help and the strength Polish society has found in itself to respond on such a scale and so quickly are impressive, they might not be enough to carry the people forward at the same pace. Although the idea of *pospolite ruszenie* was implemented again, Jurek thinks such reactions tend to be largely emotional and not based on some underlying lasting axiology:

Listen. I think Poland is generally a country of popular mobilisation and *gofundme.PL*, when something is happening. I was saying, from the beginning, that people will last for three months tops, and get tired, and it turned out to be true, although it took about six months. And now, with the summer, we barely remember there is still a war happening, major TV stations are not reporting on it that much anymore. (PL69Jurek30aUKR)

Throughout the months since the conflict escalated, the number of negative comments about Ukraine and Ukrainian refugees across social media and news platforms has grown (Warsaw Enterprise Institute, 2023). Before the war, in comparison to immigrants and refugees from non-European nations, Ukrainians were strongly preferred, on the basis of perceived general similarity (CBOS, 2015).

Not all refugees are welcomed

To understand better how our respondents perceive Ukrainian refugees and society's response to their needs, we have also asked them about their take on the so-called border crisis with Belarus. The name refers to a political impasse and humanitarian issue related to immigrants and refugees, that attempt to pass through the dense forest area that Poland and Belarus share, which also consequently serves as a frontier of the European Union.

From the summer 2021, immigrants and refugees have been arriving to Belarus from the Middle East or North Africa with the help of various intermediaries at great cost, who promised to swiftly deliver them to the Polish/EU border. As of February 2023, the total number of people who have tried to cross the green border between Poland and Belarus was 2100 (Wprost.pl, 2023). The reaction of the Polish government was harshly negative, refusing most refugee applications and pushing those applying for asylum back, breaking international agreements Poland has previously signed (bip.brpo.gov.pl, 2022). A number of non-governmental organisations, with the support of some opposition politicians, offer help on the Polish side of the green border, seeking to help those lost in the heavily forested area (Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights, 2021). The humanitarian help they gave was deemed illegal (Wądołowska, 2022). The border crisis has been a matter of controversy across the society, and one of the major issues around which political divides have unfolded in recent years. Let's have a look at the dominant attitudes toward Ukrainian refugees through the lens of how Polish society has been towards other kinds of refugees.

Michał, a programmer in his early 40 who lives close to the Ukrainian border, thinks that one of the reasons Polish helped Ukrainians was to provoke and spite the ruling PiS party, who has been pushing a strong anti-refugee rhetoric since 2015 (REF). Some commentators see

the 2015 migrant crisis, the beginning of the increased wave of refugees and migrants from the Middle East and North Africa, as one of the major reasons the Law and Justice Party has won the parliamentary elections in 2016, building its strength on anti-refugee sentiments and fears (Narkowicz, 2018). In 2015 close to 1,3 million people came to Europe through the Mediterranean Sea seeking better living conditions, the majority of them Syrian refugees fleeing civil war (Almustafa, 2022). The then staggering number is nowhere close to the amount of Ukrainian refugees that seek refuge in the EU since the Russian attack on the 24th February 2022. Michal points out that now there is no problem to help, collect funds, share the table, share beds, open up home to those in need, and that *“the society is fed up with this hypocrisy”* (PL62Michal40a), the double standards in a country that declares to be standing strong by Christian values. He thinks, however, that:

Our problem with cultural diversity hasn't changed overnight by the war. All the media were talking about those young people on the border, people with a different skin colour. So it's not only the politicians, but also the people, flooded with disinformation. Here the media were clear. There was no doubt. But it doesn't mean we are suddenly open to all immigrants coming from poverty. People are still dying trying to cross the green border with Belarus. (PL62Michal40a)

Several other respondents, who share Michal's left-leaning political inclinations, mentioned “refugee discrimination” in the context of the difference between the reaction of the Polish state towards the Belarussian border crisis and the war in Ukraine. Jerzy sees the reasons for Polish attitudes towards other cultures in our history, because *“after World War II Poland was a very homogeneous country, where there were either no representatives of other cultures, or they were assimilated”* (PL51Jerzy20a). Jerzy points out how right-wing or far-right parties *“use atavistic fears towards people of a different culture or skin colour”* to gain votes, *“completely disregarding the fact that there were many Muslims in Poland in modern times, as well as Jews”*, as well as ignoring a growing need for labour force, due to large numbers of Polish migration West (PL51Jerzy20a).

Some interviews point out the close geographical proximity of Ukraine as the main reason for the difference in reaction to the two refugee crises. Kamila, an architect in her late thirties, believes that *“if Syria was in the place of Ukraine, geographically, we would have a very different situation”* (PL75Kamila30bUKR). Mira, who has a corporate administrative job and is in her late twenties, thinks that the reason why the West got so involved in the conflict, the reasons this refugee crisis became so publicised, is *“the fact that it is so close to the EU, so close to the so-called Western world let's say culturally and religiously, Ukraine is definitely closer to the Western world than what is happening in the Middle East”* (PL76Mira20bUKR).

Some of our interviewees revoke other comments on the Belarussian border crisis, that focus on the fact that the crisis, inflated by Belarussian regime, who does nothing to prevent those dangerous illegal forest crossings, is a form of hybrid war by Russia-supported Belarus against the EU. Kamila heard it from her parents, and while she doesn't think they are wrong, agreeing that the crisis is very political in that exact manner, the real humanitarian issue is suffering lack of attention and support from the society and organisations (PL75Kamila30bUKR). Klaudia, who have helped many Ukrainian refugees, shares her views, saying that *“those people, on the border with Belarus, are not guilt of being manipulated”*, but she thinks people are afraid, and it's fear that rules their judgement of those refugees (PL72Klaudia50a).

Kazimierz, an art expert in his early 60s, thinks Poland has a problem with different cultures, and that *“while there are many foreigners from African continent or Asia living in Poland, they try not to stand out, not be too noticeable, because they know Poland isn’t really all that friendly towards other cultures”* and the ruling party is using it to *“sow fear and implement harsh policies, such as building a wired fence in the middle of one of the most precious nature reserves, Białowieża, that we share with Belarus”* (PL74Kazimierz60a). Hania, who supports the Law and Justice party, responds to this rhetoric, saying that she is *“happy and content that they didn’t let those ‘migrants’ through, because with someone [Belarus] is flying in people from Africa by planes, in order to push them out to the West, those are no migrants to me”* (PL71Hania60b). After a moment of thought, she adds that *“the war in Ukraine would have opened up a route for these people to get into Poland, including Russian spies, as there was very little control on this side”* (PL71Hania60b).

3.3 Summary

The Russian invasion of Ukraine has had an unprecedented impact on Polish society. Based on the data we collected and several public opinion surveys, we have developed an analysis of various ways the war has touched Polish society, the state and the economy, and our interviewees individually. We reconstructed various views of the Russian aggression, the Ukrainian response, and the refugee crisis the war has caused. Based on the opinions and experiences shared with us we were able to show how under the impact of the conflict and the post-pandemic economic crisis people’s understanding of the Polish-Ukrainian relations changed, as they started revising many narratives that had developed around the complex common history that can be traced back several centuries.

The war became a total event that united Poles, at least in the first weeks after 24 February 2022. While the initially massive popular mobilisation to aid Ukraine and Ukrainian refugees dwindled over time and the war next door became “the new normal”, most Poles continued to express strong support for Ukraine and its citizens, including the Ukrainian refugees, as public opinion polls amply demonstrate. Irrespective of political preferences and divergent construals of the common history, Poles continued to express their sympathy and willingness to help, although their enthusiasm started declining, under the impact of galloping inflation in the post-pandemic economy, as well as growing exhaustion, as most aid efforts were spontaneous and organised bottom-up, without much state support.

Interestingly, the Russo-Ukrainian war seems to have provided the Polish government with an opportunity to blunt the criticism it had been facing from several European Union institutions that started punishing Poland for what most observers agree are serious violations of the rule of law and the EU regulations. The government’s strategy to wait and see what the society’s response to the crisis would be paid off, strengthening the country’s position on the international stage, both within Europe and globally. Internally, the government received a lot of criticism for its lack of swift reaction to the wave of refugees, but internationally it improved its reputation.

Several respondents expressed their unhappiness with the double-standard detectable both in the actions of the Polish government and in people’s attitudes. While the attitude towards Ukrainian refugees was by and large positive, the refugees from Africa and the Middle East

who were pushed through the Polish-Belorussian border by Lukashenka's thugs were treated often with hatred and disdain. This revealed a racist system of categorisation existing in some layers of Polish culture. And while this realisation upset some people, mostly on the left, the right did not see the problem, while for quite a few people it was a non-issue (Wądołowska 2022).

4. The Czech case

“Solidarity is a beautiful thing, but this is at our expense” (“*Solidarita je krásná věc, ale tohle je na úkor nás*”)

Martina (30a)

4.1 Context

4.1.1 *The new government and its challenges*

The latest Czech parliamentary elections, which took place on November 9, 2021 have brought about a significant shift in the distribution of political power in the country. The SPOLU (*Together*), a coalition composed of centre-right and right-wing parties ODS, TOP09 and KDU-ČSL (*Civic Democratic Party, TOP09, Christian Democrats*) lost to Babiš' populist ANO only by 0.67% of the vote. ANO was in power in the previous electoral term (2018-2021), but was unable to form a governing coalition. The new government was formed by the coalition SPOLU and another centre-right coalition PirSTAN (*The Czech Pirate Party and The Mayors and Independents*), claiming the “democratic bloc's” (as they labelled themselves) victory over oligarchic populism. On November 28, Petr Fiala, the leader of ODS, was named the Prime Minister.

In addition to SPOLU's victory, the 2021 parliamentary elections led to another major political shift. For the first time in the modern history of the Czech Republic, none of the left-wing parties entered the parliament. Both traditional left-wing powerhouses, the Communist party (KSČM) and the Social Democrats (ČSSD) have lost the elections. Given the country's communist past and the extensive secularism of Czech society, such development was not only significant, but also deeply symbolic. The Czech parliament currently comprises a mix of the right and centre-right liberal and conservative governing coalition (SPOLU, The Pirate Party and STAN) and the far-right and technocratic populist opposition (SPD and ANO). From among those who voted in the 2021 election, over 1 million voters have casted a void vote, choosing a party that didn't get into the parliament. Thus, a staggering $\frac{1}{5}$ of all those who took part in the elections won't have their chosen parliamentary representative to advocate for their needs (ČeskáTelevize 2021).

The election campaign of the victorious ‘democratic bloc’ was ascribed the significance of a moral battle between good (SPOLU: democratic, western-oriented, progressive) and evil (populist, authoritarian, backwards – represented by ANO, KSČM and SPD) by the coalition politicians and their supporters. The representatives of the ‘democratic bloc’ promised to bring about positive political change. Nevertheless, the internal divisions among the individual coalition partners on critical political issues such as equal marriage or climate change, have raised important questions about what shape will the promised change take and how ‘western’ is it actually going to be. Interestingly, the leading coalition party ODS, which stylises itself as the main force to put an end to an era of A. Babiš' populist politics, has cooperated closely

with the Law and Justice party (the Polish national conservatives) in the euro-critical club of MEPs (Slačálek 2021: 165). Another instance is the consistent effort of the current Minister of Labour and Social Affairs M. Jurečka to push the conservative agenda to influence family policy.

The Czech response to war in Ukraine

Not long after being elected, the new government was faced with a rapidly growing inflation, induced by two years of the Covid-19 pandemic. Russia's war in Ukraine, and its unprecedented impact on the global market, has escalated other already severe social and political issues out of proportion, creating the most impactful economic crisis since the 2008 GFC. Like other European governments, but perhaps even more so given the geographical proximity and historical legacy of the CEE countries, the new Czech government had to take a clear stand on the conflict. Immediately after the Russian invasion on February 24th, the PM Fiala made a public appearance denouncing Russia's aggression, stating that the Czech government was prepared to accommodate Ukrainian refugees and participate in the economic sanctions against the Russian Federation, including the interruption of the supplies of Russian gas (ČeskáTelevize 2022).

In the weeks that followed, the government has brought forward a set of policies focused on the administration, aid and integration of Ukrainian refugees titled Lex Ukrajina (Rozhlas 2022a). The package included a 'humanitarian benefit' worth up to 5,000 CZK (≈ 205 EUR), which any Ukrainian citizen who has fled the country after February 24th would be eligible for. The Czech Republic became one of the top four countries to receive Ukrainian refugees, welcoming 462,622 of them³. The top three are Russia (2,852,395), Poland (1,507,893), and Germany (1,021,667). Out of the four, it has received the highest number of Ukrainian refugees per capita (Reliefweb 2022).

In addition to refugee aid, the Czech government has pledged to provide military support to Ukraine by sending weapons worth of 400 million CZK (≈16,5 million EUR). The decision has been justified by PM Fiala with the following statement: "We are at war. This is an attack against the free world, we must do everything we can to stop Putin"⁴ (iDnes 2022a).

The immediate response of Czech society to Russia's invasion of Ukraine was a nation-wide wave of solidarity, consisting of numerous pro-Ukrainian protests, convoys of material aid, offers to free up apartment spaces to accommodate refugees, or coordination of cars picking up refugees at the border. Certainly, historically such support for persons fleeing war has been unprecedented in the Czech Republic's postsocialist period.⁵

³ Data from November 22, Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1312584/ukrainian-refugees-by-country/>

⁴ Translated from the Czech original: "Jsme ve válce. Je to útok proti svobodnému světu, musíme udělat vše, abychom Putina zastavili"

⁵ The large wave of solidarity both among the wider public and the government can be assessed in a sharp contrast to the 2015 "refugee crisis". During that period, those in the CR who welcomed refugees fleeing the war in the Middle East and North Africa were in significant minority and were often demonised for their support by the rest of the Czech society.

Figure 2: Photo of a solidarity demonstration with Ukraine, Prague - Vaclavske Namesti, February 24 2022 © Zewlakk

Nevertheless, with the passing of time the initial enthusiasm subsided as the prices of energy and basic amenities started to increase. A recent sociological survey has shown a decline in levels of Czech support for Ukraine since the beginning of the war, primarily as a result of growing public concern over the rising costs of living, partially associated with the ongoing war (STEM 2022b). The public became worried with the rapidly increasing prices of their energy bills and basic amenities.

In the span of Kralova's fieldwork, she started to notice expressions of this phenomenon in the digital sphere. Given the government's wide support of Ukraine, Facebook users would frequently evoke their sympathy or animosity towards the new right-wing government as a way to assert their position on the conflict. With the dwindling public enthusiasm for the broad support of Ukraine, the surging economic crisis, and a perceived lack of solutions or clear communication from the government, certain social groups have grown increasingly dissatisfied. In a similar way as during the Covid-19 pandemic, disinformation surrounding the war started spreading quickly across social media, including Facebook groups and pages. As a result, online spaces where issues related to the Ukrainian conflict were discussed has transformed into a space of extreme polarisation.

4.1.2 Polarisation

The specific setup of social media platforms, particularly Facebook and its in-built system of algorithms, tends to amplify the loudest (and more radical) voices. Comments which receive the highest number of reactions from other Facebook users make it to the top of the discussions, instantly drawing attention of the incoming discussion participants. This process

tends to generate one-sided reactions and heated exchanges, with contributors eagerly expressing their disagreement or affinity with a given statement. This is especially true about polarising topics such as the Covid-19 pandemic, or in this case the war in Ukraine and the government's handling thereof.

In the Czech online spaces which I studied, I noticed a continuation of some of the polarising dynamics which emerged during the first phase of the fieldwork focused on the Covid-19 pandemic. This involved arguments between members of the antagonistic camps, taking the form of comment exchanges between the unvaccinated versus the vaccinated, those supporting Ukraine versus those who do not, between online users in favour of the new government and those wishing for their resignation. The aims of these exchanges seemed to follow a certain pattern - rather than engaging in a constructive debate, users were primarily asserting their own views and ridiculing those opposed to them. These divisive dynamics also manifested in real life, where participants told me about instances when they had to stop talking to particular friends or family members.

One of them is Vašek (40b) from Prague, who is a strong supporter of Ukraine and has been following the Russia-Ukraine conflict since 2014. After the invasion, he decided to set up a Facebook page where he could post up-to-date information from the military front. During our conversation he mentioned that: *“Since day one of the war, a lot of my former ‘friends’ have blocked me. And it was not because of fear, but because of a conviction that they were doing the best thing, that they are saving the world and that everyone around them is a Rusophobe”* (0422vasek40bUK).

What is more, since February 23 this online polarisation has produced its own visuality. Online users actively supporting Ukraine started to include an Ukrainian flag emoji as part of their profile pictures and those against would include an emoji of a Czech flag. Such visual marking of one's political positions on social media became an essential part of an identification with one's both in and out groups, consolidating their set of morals and values regarding the crisis and signalling them to the outside world.

The symbolism of the Ukrainian and Czech flag emojis is fairly obvious. The Ukrainian flag emerged as a spontaneous expression of solidarity and affinity with Ukraine, which could also be spotted outside of the digital sphere, with Ukrainian flags hanging in the windows of apartment blocks, shops, restaurants etc. The Czech flag followed as a reaction to what some of my participants described as an excessive display of support for a foreign country and its privileging over the Czech Republic's national interests. In fact a lot of the “anti-Ukrainian” sentiments shared with me during the interviews were not based on clearly pro-Russian views or even lack of empathy with the Ukrainian people. In the vast majority, they were coming out of a persuasion that in the light of the severe economic crisis, the Czech government and their supporters were primarily concerned for Ukraine, while completely disregarding the growing economic struggles of ‘their own people’ (*naši lidé*). The second commonly expressed concern was the perceived threat of a loss of the Czech national pride and nationalism in general, which was elaborated on by Bohuna (50b), who works as a primary school teacher in a small town in South-Moravian Region:

What I am a bit distressed about is... I just sent money to Ukraine, we have Ukrainians in our schools, we are trying to help. But when I go around the town and I see the high

school decorated only with Ukrainian flags... well I went into the classroom and said: “Come on kids, let's sing our Czech national anthem, it is soon going to be the Liberation Day (end of WWII)”. So from now on we are singing our national anthem everyday and tomorrow I will bring the Czech flag into the classroom, because I feel like the children have already forgotten how it looks. (0522bohuna50aUK)

We will return to this phenomenon in more detail in the main section of the report, but for now it suffices to observe that the use of the Ukrainian/Czech flag emojis served as an important polarising factor in the social media discussions which we observed.

Another way in which these polarisations manifested themselves were the pro-Ukrainian and ‘pro-Czech’ protests. The former started to take place soon after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, organised mainly by *Milion Chvilek pro Demokracii (A Million Moments for Democracy)* - a pro-government civil society organisation which stood behind a series of earlier nation-wide protests against the former government of Andrej Babiš in 2018 (iDnes 2022b). The latter occurred for the first time on a larger scale only in September 2022. Coined with a slogan: “The Czech Republic in 1st place - yes to peace and prosperity, no to the war and misery” (*Česká republika na 1. místě - mír a prosperitu, ne válku a bídu*), the protest was organised by a conglomerate of established far right politicians, anti-systemic civil society activists (large part of whom were affiliated with the ‘anti-covid’ movement) and new aspiring political parties. Its overriding theme was an uncompromising critique of the new government and its mishandling of the energy and economic crises, calling for the government’s resignation. Their mobilising discourses were not ‘anti-Ukrainian’ per se, nevertheless elements of pro-Russian sentiments were carefully concealed behind slogans about the need for energy security (allowing Russian gas supplies to the Czech Republic), geopolitical stability (not taking sides in the conflict), anti-globalism (critique of the EU and NATO) and the privileging Czech citizens (for example, by not taking in Ukrainian refugees) (iDnes 2022c).

Figure 3: Photo of an anti-government demonstration, Prague Vaclavske Namesti, September 3 2022, © Kamaryt Michal

The first September protest in Prague was well attended (an estimate of 70,000 protesters), and initiated a series of future protests around the country, which were not as big but still attracted a relatively large number of participants. In reaction to the protest on September 3, PM Fiala made a public statement essentially claiming that the attendees were victims of Russian propaganda and disinformation campaigns (Novinky.cz 2022). This has infuriated many people including some of my research participants, who either sympathised with or themselves attended these anti-government demonstrations but who did not support Russia. They were also convinced that the mainstream media and particularly the main public television Česká Televize (ČT, Czech Television) deeply misrepresented these events. They claimed that ČT has purposefully underestimated the numbers of attendees of the anti-government protests while exaggerating the numbers of the pro-Ukrainian ones. When I asked Ludmila (50a), who works as an accountant in Prague and who started attending these 'anti-government' protests already during the pandemic, why she thinks that the media would provide biased information, her response was:

Because they are ordered to do so. Media are not allowed to inform us about these things. Angelika Bazalova (journalist) posted on her social media that she was going to write the truth about the Covid vaccines for Deník N (independent online newspaper, liberal/progressive) and they said they will not publish it. Before we did not use to read Parlamentní listy (an online newspaper, considered by the mainstream to be disinformation media channel), but now we do. (0322ludmila50aUK)

In the narratives of my research participants, the media figured as a main instrument of division. It was also one of the most frequently articulated subjects of criticism during the Covid-19 phase of my fieldwork - participants across political spectrum were telling me of having developed a strong distaste towards the oversaturation of the main media with Covid-19-related news.

Participants who were sceptical towards the mainstream narratives around the Covid-19 pandemic gradually grew a strong distrust, and in some cases even contempt towards traditional media sources. Often, the primary content of the numerous 'anti-covid' alternative social media groups and channels was focused on the supposed lies that the mainstream politicians and medical institutions promoted about the Covid-19 virus and the vaccination. The mainstream media were then perceived as the main propaganda machine of this so-called global conspiracy. Participants following the 'anti-covid' movement were telling me that they started to resent the mainstream media completely, that they did not even bother to put the TV on anymore because of the utter lies they broadcasted, and that Facebook channels became the primary source of information for them. The growing media distrust which has escalated during the pandemic should certainly be a point of concern as it continues to shape people's perception of the ongoing war in Ukraine (and the consumption of the war-related disinformation).

Martina (30a) has primarily worked in hospitality throughout her adult life and the Covid-19 restrictions have left her unemployed. During the pandemic she started following various 'anti-covid' channels and currently feels uneasy about the Czech government's active support of

Ukraine. When I asked her whether she believed that the Covid-19 virus was artificially created, her response illuminated some of the issues of media distrust and its effects:

I think that there's some truth about the theory that it was artificially created. I do not believe the version that they are pressing onto us. It is the same with the news about Ukraine. It is so obvious. Three years ago if you put the evening news on, there were several topics discussed, properly addressed. Today, there is only one topic talked about over and over again. They make us stupid. And the people believe it. They say that in Russia there is propaganda. But we have the exact same propaganda here (0422martina30aUK).

Angelika (50a) who lives in a small town in Central Bohemia and who stayed at home throughout the pandemic with her five children did not get vaccinated, because she believes that her immunity is strong enough to protect her. When we talked about the pandemic, her response also highlighted important connections between the mistrust towards the mainstream interpretations of the pandemic and those related to the war.

Because the doctors used to get more money for it (if it was death from Covid). So for example our friend, who we know died because he fell from a scaffold, supposedly also died because of Covid. They keep lying to us and so one does no longer even believe the news about the developments in Ukraine. The wave has started and people do not believe anything anymore. I see lots of hysterics, people are divided and it is not good. It shouldn't matter if I am vaccinated or not, if I am helping Ukrainians or not. I am human and we all have the same rights (0522angelika50aUK).

The network of the 'anti-covid' movement⁶ and its strong influence online was instrumental in cultivating and reinforcing this mistrust in mainstream political, medical and media institutions. While these groups varied in nature, it is possible to trace their links to various previously existing far-right groups and actors, who gained most visibility during the 2015 'refugee crisis'. Since the pandemic ceased to be the primary topic of media attention and was replaced by headlines about the war in Ukraine, the majority of the well-established 'anti-covid' spokespeople redirected their focus accordingly. As such we are currently witnessing a shift in the discourse of these groups, which have previously centred around the Covid-19 conspiracies and today base their mobilisation strategy on anti-Ukrainian and anti-establishment sentiments, conflating them with the undergoing economic crises (as highlighted earlier). Moreover, with the influx of Ukrainian refugees, part of this growing illiberal movement is becoming increasingly aggressive and violent in their xenophobic and pro-Russian rhetoric. For instance, on October 27 2022 a couple of men active in the 'anti-covid' movement - Patrik Tušl and Tomáš Čermák - were sentenced to 6 and 10 months in prison for inciting violence against Ukrainian refugees on their social media (iRozhlas 2022b).

It is important to stress that participants who shared with me certain anti-Ukrainian sentiments were, apart from a couple of exceptions, never so extreme in their views. Nevertheless, looking at Table 1, it is possible to draw a clear parallel between those who were sceptical of the official stance on the Covid-19 pandemic and those who became sceptical towards the

⁶ Number of civil society initiatives, groups and aspiring political parties, vaguely united in their opposition to the covid-19 restrictions.

mainstream narratives about the war in Ukraine. The intensifying dynamic of polarisation which I briefly outlined in this section can serve as a partial explanation for this. In what follows, I will provide a more detailed analysis of the research participants' main positions on first, the conflict in Ukraine and second, the acceptance of Ukrainian refugees to the Czech Republic. The ensuing discussion should help to further substantiate and nuance the diverse perspectives on those issues.

4.2 Analysis of the Ethnographic Data

This section illuminates the key themes which emerged from interviews with research participants about the Russo-Ukrainian war. In order to capture the main trends, we have classified the participants' accounts based on their political leanings, as this largely determined their stances on the issues in question. For the sake of analytical clarity, I reduced the seven political leanings as highlighted in the methodological section into three main categories. These derive from participants' moral values and their general ideas about the preferred societal organisation, rather than their approaches to the economy. Just to emphasise again, these categories are fairly fluid and subjected to inconsistencies.

Conservative participants (including right-wing libertarians, right-wing conservatives, left-wing conservatives) In general, this group consisted of participants with conservative and authoritarian moral values, with strong anti-globalist and some anti-Western leanings. Economically speaking, their approaches ranged from conservative laissez faire to more state-interventionist. This group demonstrated the highest levels of mistrust towards the mainstream political, medical and media institutions and held anti-establishment and anti-government views. A lot of these participants were sceptical towards official interpretations of the pandemic and of the war in Ukraine. The majority no longer used mainstream media channels to get information and instead switched to alternative online (and some disinformation) channels. Demographically, respondents of this group were from mid-sized and smaller cities and towns with an average age range between 40-70 years old.

Liberal participants (including right-wing liberals, centre-right liberals) This group consisted of economically conservative (neoliberal) and liberally minded individuals. Their views were primarily pro-Western oriented, with some levels of EU scepticism. These participants were generally open to some levels of 'social justice' reforms such as equal marriage or refugee inclusion, but would not go as far as to actively advocating for them. They demonstrated high to moderate levels of trust towards public institutions and the system of liberal democracy as a whole. This group was mostly pro-government (SPOLU) and supported the government's stance on actively helping Ukraine in the conflict. Demographically these respondents were from large and mid-sized cities and towns with an average age range between 30-50 years old.

Progressive participants (including centre-left progressives, left progressives) This group has the smallest representation in the whole dataset, nevertheless constitutes a relevant stance on the issues in question. Their approaches to the economy were overall neoliberal but stressing the need for state-interventionism and implementation of redistributive and more socially just economic measures. The participants had strongly progressive views and some even actively participated in social justice campaigns for causes such as equal marriage,

refugee integration etc. This group was critical of the SPOLU government, primarily because of their perceived austerity politics and conservative values. They were nevertheless appreciative of the government's pro-Ukraine stance and the acceptance of refugees. Demographically these respondents were from large and mid-sized cities and towns with an average age range between 20-50 years old.

4.2.1 *The Conflict in Ukraine*

According to the data from the latest sociological survey (November 2022), which investigated the Czech citizens' perceptions of the Ukrainian conflict, there are currently only about 3-4% of Czechs with strong pro-Russian views (STEM 2022b). Nevertheless, in comparison to a previous survey from April 2022 (STEM 2022a), Czech citizens' concern for post-war recovery of Ukraine has been declining steadily. Another decrease has been registered in the positive assessment of Ukraine - while in April 2022, only ¼ of people assessed the country negatively, this November already 39% of Czechs held negative views of Ukraine (and 30% held clearly positive views). Furthermore, the latest international research comparing the experiences and perceptions of the war among citizens of six different countries (Ukraine, Poland, Czech Republic, Georgia, Estonia and Israel) indicated that 67% of Czech citizens perceive the war in Ukraine as the biggest threat to their national economy. Finally, contrary to the Czech PM's statement "We are at war", the majority of respondents stated that they did not feel that this war was theirs. In consequence, the Czech respondents do not see the benefits of investing public resources in the war, as they feel that in the current context of the economic crisis, the financial support should be directed towards the Czech population (Kubová 2022).

Perspectives of conservative participants

As the surveys highlighted above have shown, a very small percentage of the population actually openly claims to be pro-Russian or support Russia in their war efforts. There must therefore be other underlying reasons which lead to this dwindling support of Ukraine among sections of the Czech citizens. Based on my conversations with the conservative respondents, I identified the following narratives:

The first one was structured around the discourse of peace and peaceful solutions. Participants felt uncomfortable that the Czech government was using finances derived from taxpayers' money to buy and ship weapons to Ukraine. They felt that by doing that, the Czechs were directly participating in the war and by extension in the killing of human lives. They were arguing that the need for a peaceful solution, so widely advocated for by the Western leaders, was irreconcilable with the use of armed force. This sentiment is evoked in the following statement by Martina (30b), who was quoted earlier: *"I think the stance of the Ukrainian president is really stupid. The soldiers are fighting and he has time for video calls and tweeting stuff like 'Send weapons'. But I think that if the weapons were not being sent, the war would be long over. I do not see Ukraine as so innocent."* (0422martina30aUK)

Bronislav (50b), who is from a mid-sized city in the Olomouc region and himself once used to work as a soldier, argued that a peaceful solution and arms shipments are in conflict. When we asked him what his stance on the conflict was, he replied: *"Listen, I know what is going on in Ukraine. This is war, and because I was myself fighting in the war, I know there is always a*

necessity to look for peaceful solutions”, he continues by asking, “do any of the Western politicians really want a peaceful solution? Did you notice anything like that? Everyone just says: ‘Let’s arm them, let’s arm them!’” (0522bronislav50aUK).

When the interviewer tried to suggest that Ukraine did not have many other options to choose from but to arm itself in order to protect its existence as a sovereign state, some conservative participants would then bring up conspiratorial claims, that none of ‘us’ (ordinary people) really knew what was going on. Following statement by Pavlina (50b), a single-mum of three children who has worked precarious jobs her whole life, is one of the several examples of such narrative:

I do not agree with the Russian invasion, but Ukrainians are stupid in this regard and I suspect that this whole conflict was artificially created and maintained. If Putin really wanted, he would erase them (Ukrainians) from this world and he did not do that. I also think that he actually wants to find a peaceful solution. (0322pavlina50bUK)

The pervasive feeling that something bigger is happening ‘behind the curtains’ is a reoccurring sentiment, which has been repeated to us multiple times, particularly by the ‘anti-covid’ supporters / sceptics during both phases of the digital fieldwork. Vilem (60b) is a Roma-origin pensioner who lives in a mid-sized town in Central Bohemia and who has worked his whole life in diplomacy. Despite being very well educated with fairly high levels of social capital, even Vilem admitted that in the past couple of years, he was losing trust in the mainstream narratives about the current events. His mistrust was incited by the Covid-19 pandemic to which he lost his three family members, some of whom, he suspects, died because of the vaccination. As he explains, *“I do not know, I feel like all of the events of the past period...and I am no do not believe in conspiracy theories...but I feel like it’s an initiation of something new, something which should put an end to the old orders [...] I would say that the coronavirus was kind of a foreshadowing for the events which are happening today” (0322vilem60bUK).*

Kralova and Vilem ended up discussing the issue of desinformation in the Roma community, because both in the case of Covid-19 and the current war, large sections of the Roma populations turned to conspiracy theories. According to Vilem, one of the reasons for this is the Roma’s inherent mistrust towards the society, politicians and the media, which have for the past decades been spreading misinformation about their community and did not make any efforts to protect them from structural poverty and racial violence. Nevertheless, as highlighted earlier, desinformation was affecting larger sections of the society than just the Romas. In the interviews with conservative respondents, one of the views for why the Czech Republic should not support Ukraine was also the claim of fascism and nazism in Ukraine. This, as we know, has become one of the most commonly circulated claims of Russia’s hybrid war.

Conservative respondents also talked frequently about impartiality in reference to the war in Ukraine. They argued that their country should not interfere in conflicts and wars which are not theirs. The following quote by Bronislav (who was mentioned previously) well sums up this position: *“I am for the self-determination of every nation. How they have it or do not have it, that should be their concern. As I think that the EU should not interfere into our personal matters, then equally we should not interfere into the matters of Ukraine. They have to deal with this on their own” (0522bronislav50aUK).* Views of such kind could be partially explained by the declining levels of trust towards international organisations such as the European Union

and NATO, especially among the conservative parts of Czech society. The hope for collective solutions is consistently extremely low, which was one of the key findings of the previously mentioned comparative research (Kubová 2022). Alice Koubová, the main investigator for the Czech segment of this study, stresses that among the six studied countries, Czech respondents have demonstrated the lowest levels of trust and hope for successful solutions of the crisis and better collective future in general.

Among other reasons for impartiality, the potential threat to the Czech national security potentially caused by the alliance with the West came to the fore. Simply put it was the fear that the Czech Republic could become the next country to invade on Putin's list. The second part of this narrative was linked to the ongoing energy crisis. Some of the participants stated that they felt comfortable receiving Russian gas, if that meant that their energy bills would be stabilised and would not further increase. This is for instance illustrated by the following statement by Pavlina (50b): *"The hysteria around Germany's continued reliance on Russian gas. And so what? Why shouldn't they? Do they think that Biden will help us?! [...] Business is business. It has nothing to do with politics"* (0322pavlina50bUK). The following Bronislav's quote also further supports this sentiment, when he criticises the Czech government for stopping the supplies of Russian gas: *"If Fiala did not play the hero and started negotiating with Russia about gas prices, in one month the energy crisis would be resolved. And every good politician would do that - to protect the interests of their people"* (0522bronislav50aUK).

Finally, an interesting historical reference was brought up by Alena (50a), who works as an accountant in a mid-sized city in one of the poorest regions of the Czech Republic: *"We also did not receive any help during World War II. Who helped us? No one. Why do they think that they can just come here and get everything for free without doing anything? We also do not print the money here for free, we have to work for them!"* (0522alena50aUK). Alena's account evokes the painful national memory of treason referring to the Munich accords, where none of the world's powers stood up to protect Czechoslovakia's freedom. Her narrative also points out to the importance of meritocracy, which is highly valued in Czech society and will be elaborated on in more depth in the next section on perceptions of the Ukrainian refugees.

Perspectives of liberal participants

Overall, liberal participants saw Russia's invasion of Ukraine as a breach of international law and an act of naked aggression. They widely condemned Putin's decision to invade Ukraine and thought that taking a clear stance against it was a question of basic ethics. Some of them, such as Vašek (40b) (cited earlier), felt a need to spread the awareness of what has been going on in the conflict since 2014 and so he started a Facebook page, where he could counter misinformation and provide up-to-date facts. His take on the conspiracy theories is as follows: *"In Czech there are a lot of people who do not understand who the aggressor is (since 2014) and they uncritically side with Putin's system. They do not see that there's dictatorship in Russia and some of them actually admire it. Paradoxically they then complain that there is no freedom of speech in Czech."* (0422vasek40bUK)

Others have shared with us their despair over the war developments and a real shock which they felt when they learnt about the invasion. Leila (30a) who lives in a mid-sized town in the Moravian-Silesian Region and spent the pandemic on maternity leave said

that: *“It really saddens me, that in today’s times...when one thinks that we live in a fairly civilised age, where people are generally hesitant to use weapons, that basically so close to us a war started...it makes me sick.”* (0422leila30aUK)

The geographical proximity evoked by Leila was commonly mentioned as a reason by other liberal participants for why it was so important for the Czech Republic to provide active support of Ukraine in the conflict. Interestingly, while the conservative participants believed that if the Czech government got too involved in the conflict, it would create a threat to national security, the liberal participants were convinced that the country would become endangered if it did not get engaged deeply enough. Some of the participants in the liberal category believed that if Putin was not stopped, the Czech Republic could become his next military target. The collective memory of 1968 crushed Prague Spring has certainly played a role in the construction of this narrative, as the quote of Monika (50b) demonstrates:

I am really angered by the development of this war. Of course in Syria for instance they also attacked civilians, but it was possible to close eyes to that. Here, with our historical experience with Russia and the way in which the Russian trolls spread misinformation, influence elections etc... It's kind of like a general anger towards their regime as a whole. (0422monika50aUK)

The interesting point emerging from this comparison, is that both conservative and liberal participants placed importance on similar values such as national security, but interpreted such values differently. This difference might have stemmed from their divergent lived experiences, where participants from the conservative sample tend to feel more economically insecure and therefore attach bigger importance to more immediate and material concerns such as energy security. These findings raise interesting wider questions about the nature of solidarity and mutual aid, to which we will turn in more depth in the following section.

Perspectives of progressive participants

Generally speaking, the progressive participants’ perspectives on the Russo-Ukrainian war did not differ from the liberal ones. All of the representatives of this group condemned the war and felt that it was important to support Ukraine, both in terms of military aid and provision of asylum for Ukrainian refugees. Some suggested that support could be even greater, such as Laura (30b) who currently lives in Germany where she moved to work as a university professor:

I am glad that the Czech government is helping. I think they could also give more to the refugees than just 5000 CZK for the rent. We were hosting a family here in Germany and when I saw how much Germany is helping, I realised that in Czechia we are not so solidary. What I am more bothered by is how we (Czechs) are unwilling to help any other war refugees. Even with the case of the fifty Christian Syrian children which the government refused to take in because it was too much...and suddenly 300 thousands of Ukrainians is not a problem. (0522laura30bUK)

Apart from the double standard (which will be analysed later in this report), Laura's quote provides an interesting comparative insight into the German case. Nevertheless, given Germany's economic position and its recent history of large-scale refugee integration, it is not surprising that it is able to provide more support than the Czech Republic.

The final point worth highlighting, which emerged from the interviews with the progressive participants, is their views on the sections of the Czech society which did not straight away condemn Putin (which is represented in this report by the conservative participants sample). Liberal participants, when asked about why they thought some of the fellow citizens downplayed Russia's aggression, responded by claiming that those people (conservative respondents) held such views because they were backwards, uneducated or unable to empathise with others. This kind of discourse is well illustrated for instance by Leila (30a) (who was quoted earlier): *"Because here, when they were throwing morons from the sky, most of them fell into our region. I have this feeling that here in North of Moravia lives a lot of, let's say, less intelligent people... or as my husband says: dumb beasts (tupá hovada)... it is bad to say it like that, but when I read those (anti-Ukrainian) comments, I do think it's true"* (0422leila30aUK).

Such scorn heaped on people of middle-lower and working class backgrounds by certain members of the middle classes who tend to be liberal in their outlook has also come up during the first phase of the Covid-19 fieldwork (Davidov *et al* 2022). There is a pervasive tendency in Czech society to blame individuals and families' socio-economic difficulties on their personal failures or even, as alluded to by Leila, on some sort of inherent flaw in their character. On the contrary, more progressive participants see these attitudes as having a deeper structural basis, rooted in decades of neoliberal governance, which disregarded the grievances of the precarious populations. Max (30a), who is a musician based in Prague and who defines himself as leftist, explains it as follow:

In reality, I think that poor and marginalised people are not so bothered by the refugees. They are more bothered by the lies of the government: 'sorry there is no money, we don't have resources for social spending etc.' Of course that they have these resources and you can see it now in this unprecedented wave of refugee aid. Again, this is totally fine, but unfortunately it is clear that this lack of resources was a complete lie. This is absolutely nothing against the refugees or the government's help to them... it is the fact that we have resources, they are just not allocated appropriately. (0522max30aUK)

Overall, the views of the progressive participants resemble, more or less, the approach of the progressive wing of Western social democracy. In the context of the Czech Republic, where none of the traditionally left-wing parties have any real representation, the progressive participants feel politically disillusioned. This is first of all because issues relevant to their everyday lives such as affordable housing, climate change (greener cities) or LGBTQ+ rights tend to be overlooked by the liberal and conservative right-wing parties in power. Second, the progressive participants mentioned the link between the right-wing government's weak social politics, lack of redistributive economic measures and a general disregard for the impoverishing population and the rise and popularity of extreme right-wing and populist parties. Consequently, the progressive participants see the growing popularity of these

'undemocratic' political actors, whose beliefs and values are in sharp contrast with their own, as dangerous. Since the beginning of the conflict in February 2022, extreme right-wing discourses, particularly around the issues of Ukrainian refugees, have become more pronounced in the public sphere.

4.2.2 *The Ukrainian refugees*

As has been iterated earlier, since the beginning of the war, the Czech Republic has accepted the highest number of Ukrainian refugees in Europe per capita (ReliefWeb 2022). Nevertheless, after the initial wave of solidarity, the support and will to help started to deteriorate. This has been confirmed by the aforementioned comparative study (Kubová 2022) which shows that out of all the studied countries (Ukraine, Poland, Czech Republic, Georgia, Estonia and Israel), Czech citizens have demonstrated the lowest levels of support for Ukrainian refugees. Anxieties over the generous intake of Ukrainian refugees and its perceived economic consequences for the local population have been articulated most strongly by sections of the population represented in this report by the conservative respondents.

Perspectives of conservative participants

In the span of our conversations with the conservative participants about the incoming Ukrainian refugees to the Czech Republic, several recurring narratives have emerged. By far the most common and pervasive was built around the perception that Czech citizens' material wellbeing and social stability is being threatened by the growing demands and state expenditures associated with the refugee emergency. According to their perspective, the government's decision to help refugees was at the expense of the Czech people (*naši lidé*), an expense that the participants were not willing to pay for.

Přemysl (50a) lives in a mid-sized town in South Moravia where he works in logistics for an international firm. While his family is so far managing to cope with the inflation-fueled rising prices, Přemysl expressed fears over the other, less fortunate sections of the society: *"There is a lot of Czechs with existential problems... and then you see the refugees who come and get everything for free here, they get a SIM card with unlimited credit, they get a tablet at the border...new clothes, housing benefits and all the other benefits...while Czech people have to go to work and pay for everything themselves"* (0322premysl50aUK).

What strongly emerges from Přemysl's account and what was very common across the conservative sample is the emphasis on deservingness. As was mentioned earlier and as other sociological studies (STEM 2021) confirm, for Czech society, meritocracy is a very widely shared and important value. It is essentially a belief that each person is responsible for their own social and economic wealth and gets rewarded accordingly to their efforts. This also partially explains the wide-spread demonising (and deeply racialized) discourse around social welfare recipients. For instance, when we talked to Alena (50a) (who we quoted earlier) about state welfare, she told me: *"There are families, which really don't have a choice. They have some disability, which means that the mum cannot work, or that she has to take care of the child. I understand that"*, she continues by emphasising, *"state should help these cases, it is normal and it is not happening. These families are collapsing, while the gypsies (cigáni) get*

everything without ever working [...] And this is thousands of cases. I would say 99% of the gypsies do it that way” (0522alena50aUK).

The exception to meritocracy thus applies to individuals who find themselves in an uneasy and unexpected situation due to external circumstances which they can not influence. In that case, it is actually socially expected to lend a helping hand. In theory, this would imply a wide support for people escaping the war, which still a lot of Czech citizens uphold to. Nevertheless, the narratives of the conservative participants reveal that their support for those ‘in need’ is increasingly defined alongside nativist categories. Bronislav (50b), who was quoted earlier, amplifies this sentiment:

I used to drive around and help where I could when parts of the country were affected by the tornados. I used to deliver things, whatever was needed, I know loads of people that were affected, that until today they don't have their houses fixed - but to Ukrainians we give everything for free. What is this supposed to mean? We are Czechs and we should take care of the Czech nation in the first place, no? I know so many mothers who have nowhere to live, they are sick, their children are sick... the insurance companies don't want to pay for their treatments and now we are suddenly fundraising millions for the Ukrainians? (0522bronislav50aUK)

The need to help ‘our people’ (naši lidé) first and prioritise their needs has been repeated over and over again. Pavlina (50b), who was also mentioned earlier, has first hand experience with living just above the poverty line. As a single mum of three children, she found herself in difficult socioeconomic situations on several occasions, last time during the pandemic.

I am glad that we are helping. But we shouldn't exaggerate. Because there are a lot of single mothers, seniors, or what I remember when kids were doing the online schooling, lots of children from poor socioeconomic backgrounds, their parents could not afford to get them an iPad or a good wifi. So they became essentially excluded from schooling. And the only way to overcome poverty is through education. And these kids won't be able to catch up. And the government did not give a damn about it. (0322pavlina50bUK)

When I asked Pavlina about her experiences with receiving support from the state, she told me that the system was extremely convoluted, disciplinary and humiliating. *“The way the system is set up, with all the paperwork... I became so sick of it. I ended up without rent and I was really at the bottom (na dně), but I did not want to participate in it anymore”,* she continued by saying, *“I clenched my teeth and managed to work two, three jobs... I know that social welfare is often abused, and not only by the Roma, by others as well... But this system is really a disaster” (0322pavlina50bUK).*

Pavlina's critique of the social welfare system is just one of many examples represented in this fieldwork. In the grand scheme of things, the ineffective and convoluted system of state support, combined with the aforementioned demonising discourse of ‘welfare abuse’ has led to an unhealthy perception that if things ever become worse, one cannot rely on any effective support from the state. Related to that is the common trope of ‘migrants stealing our jobs’ which actually did surface in the interviews on a couple of occasions, despite Czech having one of the consistently lowest rates of unemployment in the CEE region (Statista 2022).

Honza (30a) is originally from a smaller town in Eastern Moravia but has moved to another part of the country to work in a large car factory. Overall, he thinks that Czech Republic does not have enough resources and the necessary infrastructure to accommodate so many refugees and feels that this will also impact the job market; *“Well, when it comes to the working conditions, I think the refugees will change this significantly, because our government will try to make them work and this will create problems for ‘our people’”* (0422honza30aUK). Going back to the findings of the comparative research (Kubová 2022) which showed that 67% of Czech citizens perceive the war in Ukraine as a significant threat to the national economy, it is clear how perceptions of economic threat, fears of economic insecurity and low trust in the government deeply impact the acceptance of the Ukrainian refugees in the Czech context.

The other common narrative surrounding the acceptance of the Ukrainian refugees was again associated with meritocratic values. Participants across this group were frequently mentioning that Ukrainian refugees were arriving in the Czech Republic with expensive cars, wearing designer clothing and when they saw them in the supermarkets, their shopping carts were full (*mají plné košíky*). Consequently, respondents who could not afford any of these things and did not receive any additional benefits from the state, thought that it was unfair that Ukrainians qualified for all this extra support. Related to that is another common trope of the authentic/worthy/deserving refugee, described widely in the literature (Zetter 1988). It is associated with the set of ideas, discourses and social constructions that people make about the refugees’ expected appearance (poorly dressed, tired), attitude (gratefulness, humbleness) and socioeconomic status (poor, deprived). If any of these expectations fail, individuals start to question the authenticity of the refugees’ claims for asylum. Such tropes were around during the 2015 ‘refugee crisis’, where photos of refugees and migrants with smartphones were widely circulated online and were used as evidence for their ‘undeservingness’. They have started to reoccur in the context of the Ukrainian crisis, as Bronislav’s (50a) statement suggests:

I just heard that apparently 5,000 CZK is not enough for them. I saw a lot of refugees in other wars⁷, and I know what they look like and these ones (Ukrainians) do not look like that. In our block of flats, there is a Ukrainian family and when you ask them where they are from, they say that they were living 250 km away from the conflict, where there is no fighting. But oh well, here they get a free trip to Prague, free tickets to ZOO, nice BMW parked outside... so they take it as a nice paid trip to Czech. (0522bronislav50aUK)

Consequently, several other participants called for more stringent checks and controls at the border, expressing the concern of not having enough information about who we are letting in. Finally, the conservative participants pointed out the double standard that liberal right-wing government applied to refugees from the Middle East and North Africa and refugees from Ukraine. Participants from this group thought that it was hypocritical that the government’s statements about the need to help refugees, the importance of taking a strong moral stance in the conflict and the virtue of solidarity, applied only to some people fleeing war. Vilem (60b) who was quoted earlier, remembers the period around 2015 when large numbers of refugees from the Middle East and North Africa were trying to make a safe passage into Europe:

⁷ Bronislav used to be a soldier.

The government was scared that there could be terrorists among those refugees. But where do you have it written, that among the Ukrainians, there are no fanatics radicalised by the fascist ideology? I really don't like to remember that time (2015), I really have this bitter feeling, because there were so many people that we turned down, so many children that had to die just because NATO and EU was not active enough, they were scared of something they could not even prove. (0322vilem60bUK)

In the majority of cases, when we asked the conservative participants how they felt about accepting refugees from the Middle East and North Africa, their response was primarily negative. On the other hand, given their hesitant stance towards the Ukrainian refugees, the conservative participants' approach towards refugee aid was in fact consistent. This was however different in the case of the liberal sample.

Perspectives of liberal participants

Overall, the liberal participants' rate of acceptance of Ukrainian refugees was very high. As mentioned earlier, participants were fully supportive of the government's decision to help Ukraine (both military and by taking in refugees). For some, it was even a matter of pride. When we asked, Leila (30a) who was mentioned earlier, what she thought about the government's response to the conflict, she said that: *"Yes, I think every country should act this way and I think that while lots of people complain about Fiala (PM), then I have to say that maybe for the first time I am not ashamed of my prime minister"* (0422leila30aUK).

Nevertheless, when we were asking these participants what their view on the refugee crisis in 2015 was, the vast majority said that they were either hesitant or indifferent. In their explanation of why the Ukrainian crisis was different, they were bringing up Ukrainians' geographical proximity and cultural similarity. That Ukraine's geographical proximity was an important factor underpinning the Czech liberal participants' solidarity was already commented on in the earlier section. Regarding the acceptance of Ukrainian refugees, the point about their cultural similarity (to Czechs) was often articulated in contrast to the cultural difference and incompatibility of the refugees from North Africa and Middle East. Lukáš (40b), who currently lives in Germany where he works in an IT company, makes the following point:

I know hard-working people from the Middle East and also from Africa, but I still sense this danger of the cultural difference. The fear that if we take lots of them in and then later we realise...the issues can come up later, with the passing of generations. Look at for instance France, where the third generation of migrants from the Middle East is radicalising. With the Ukrainian immigrants I do not see this problem. (0222lukas40bUK)

Subsequently, participants emphasised the shared slavnness, Christian-based values and hardworking nature of the Ukrainians in contrast to the incompatible cultural values of the Middle Eastern and North African refugees. According to the liberal participants, cultural similarity was an important factor facilitating integration. This is likely associated with the actual experience of Ukrainian integration, as Ukrainians constituted the biggest ethnic minority in the Czech Republic, already prior to the war (Český Statistický Úřad 2021). This community was fairly well integrated and primarily filled in low paid and agency based positions on the

Czech labour market. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that while there were never any significant conflicts between the Ukrainian and the Czech communities (prior to the war), Czechs tended to look down upon Ukrainians as a cheap labour force and used to refer to them with various derogatory terms.

Interestingly, while some conservative participants saw the incoming Ukrainian refugees as a potential threat to their job security, representatives of the liberal sample emphasised this as a potential benefit to the national economy. This is illustrated again by the quote of Lukáš (40b): *“They accepted a lot of the Ukrainian refugees because they are culturally similar to us...they are hard working people, and if the government and the whole society does not mess it up, we can really benefit from them. This is what really fuelled the German economy, they were able to profit out of the migrants”* (0222lukas40bUK). This stark difference in the perspectives of the conservative and liberal participants can be easily explained by the fact that the former tend to be from working and lower class backgrounds and are therefore more likely to seek employment in similar job sectors as the Ukrainian refugees.

On the other hand, other liberal respondents saw accepting and helping the Ukrainian refugees as a matter of principle, good morals and altruism. Rost’a (30a) comes from a fairly conservative family and was quite influenced by the views of his parents up until he became an adult. Now he has his own family and when the war in Ukraine happened, he decided to volunteer for a local refugee aid network. When we asked why it was important for him to actively participate, he told us: *“It’s because I really feel for other people, I can empathise with them easily. I always try to help wherever I can. Whatever crisis there is - whether it’s Covid, Ukraine or a person living on the streets”* (0422rosta30aUK). This sentiment is reiterated by Leila, who also thinks that helping those in need is the right thing to do: *“People should be helping one another, especially in situations like this. So what if someone arrived from Ukraine in Mercedes? If it was down to me and I had to choose which car I’d leave my country with, logically I would leave behind the worse one”* (0422leila30aUK).

Perspectives of progressive participants

All the interviewed participants with progressive leanings were fully in favour of accepting Ukrainian refugees and providing them with necessary aid. In fact, almost every individual from this category (apart from a couple of exceptions) was actively helping to alleviate the refugee emergency. This was either by hosting Ukrainian families in their homes, coordinating aid and providing transportation from the border or by volunteering at the first point of entry at the Prague main train station. Their motivation for doing so is rooted in a shared belief, that every human escaping war has a right for an asylum, regardless of their origins. For this reason, during the 2015 crisis, the majority of the progressive participants were in support of taking in refugees from the Middle East and North Africa and were overall deeply disappointed about the hostile stance of the Czech government at the time. In the span of our conversations, the progressive participants often criticised the current right-wing government for their double-standards regarding the provision of asylum. Like the conservative participants, the progressives thought this was deeply hypocritical of the government. But while the former wanted to limit the refugee intake as much as possible, the latter was in favour of accepting anyone with a legitimate asylum claim. When we asked Max (30a), who was mentioned earlier, how he felt about the situation, his response was: *“I think that accepting refugees, of any origin, skin colour or conviction, is the most basic value of any European country. So of course, I am*

very happy that we are accepting Ukrainians. What I cannot stand is the hypocrisy of people like Fiala (PM), who in 2015 posed for pictures standing next to the barbed wire in Hungary⁸ and today is the biggest refugee welcomer (vítač)” (0522max30aUK).

For David (20b), the frustration was enhanced by his personal experience in the sphere of refugee activism. He was one of the founding members of Iniciativa Hlavák (Main Train Station Initiative), which was set up in 2015 in Prague to provide practical advice and aid for incoming refugees, primarily from Syria. Although the majority of the refugees then continued their journey to Germany, because the Czech Republic was not offering asylum, Initiative Hlavák and its members became a common target of verbal (and on a couple of instances physical) abuse by far-right and extreme nationalist groups. Based on his experience, David (20b) was uncertain what reaction to expect in the case of the Ukrainian crisis: *“At the beginning we did not now if to go forward with it (organised but voluntary refugee aid for Ukrainians), because given our previous experience, where people did not really want to help, we thought we wouldn’t manage it”,* he describes, *“In the end we decided to try, because it looked like the Czech society is more willing to help Ukrainians, than the Syrians.” (0522david20bUK)* As was mentioned earlier, the initial response of the public to the Ukrainian refugee emergency was extremely solidary and Iniciativa Hlavák was joined by thousands of Czech volunteers who wanted to help.

When we asked David what he thought was the reason for this double standard, he told me that part of it has to do with the pervasive racism in Czech society: *“I think that Czech society is generally racist...it’s some kind of a... I don’t know I still don’t fully comprehend it, but it’s some kind of a refusal to understand other kinds of behaviours, other cultures. Whenever there is something new, which the Czechs don’t know, they reject it and refuse to try to understand it” (0522david20bUK).* Similar explanation was provided by Miloš (30b), who has been for the past decade doing social work among the Roma community in the North-West of the country, where he is originally from. The issue of Roma discrimination surfaced also in the case of Ukrainian refugees. To give a very brief context, as the Russo-Ukrainian conflict advanced, more and more people started to flee Ukraine. Among them was a notable number of ethnic Roma Ukrainians, who nevertheless received a very different treatment from the border officials, subjecting them to additional background checks, which the ethnic Ukrainians were not required to do. In the context of the Czech Republic, this resulted in hundreds of Roma families getting stranded at the Prague main train station (Ryšavý 2022). Miloš was among the volunteers actively involved in arranging a re-settlement to a third-country, where Ukrainian Romas would be safer. In his words: *“We reached a conclusion, that it would be better to send them somewhere more West, where there is not such a high level of systematic racism and ‘antigypsism’, both from the institutions and the citizens” (0522milos30bUK).*

We asked Miloš to reflect on some of the causes of this phenomenon:

The majoritarian opinion is that Romas are bad and we don’t want them, Muslims are bad and we don’t want them. There is also a lot of disinformation and lies circulating among the people and unfortunately, the politicians often encourage it, to get more votes. Instead of addressing these lies, they just go with the discrimination. We saw it

⁸ This is a reference to Petr Fiala’s 2015 visit to the Hungarian-Croatian border, where he applauded V. Orban for building a wall at the border to keep refugees and migrants from entering Hungary.

even among policemen and firefighters. When we sent ethnic Ukrainians to the assistance centre, they dealt with them straight away. But when we sent the Roma Ukrainians, they had to wait even a whole day. (0522milos30bUK)

Overall, the progressive respondents appreciated the government's decision to take in so many Ukrainian refugees. Nevertheless, the discrepancies between the political representation and wider public's discourses and actions in 2015 and now, made the current government's approach to the crisis seem ingenuine and discriminatory.

4.3 Summary

As the findings in this report have shown, the perception of the Czech citizens is that the Russo-Ukrainian conflict dramatically interferes with the economic, social and political matters of their country. Nevertheless, the Czech citizens' assessment of their government's response to this unprecedented war is largely determined by their socioeconomic background, political leanings, values and institutional and interpersonal trust. While large-scale sociological surveys aim to provide an overall picture of emerging societal trends, the goal of this ethnographic study of the Czech networked publics is to offer more nuanced and in-depth insights into the perceptions of the ongoing crises as experienced and narrated by the people. What follows is a summary of the key findings which emerged from our research.

First, for the section of the society labelled in this study as 'conservative' - namely participants with conservative/authoritarian values, which lean toward anti-globalist and anti-Western stances, tends to be from lower and working classes and demonstrate the highest levels of institutional and political mistrust - the conflict in Ukraine has been perceived as a threat to their economic security and social stability. The previous period, characterised by the Covid-19 pandemic and its associated restrictions, has for many of them led to the precarization or loss of their jobs and as such economic security. Moreover, their pervasive disillusionment with mainstream politics and low institutional trust, enhanced by the social isolation during the Covid-19 era, meant that significant numbers turned from mainstream media to the online spaces, where disinformation has been spreading in unprecedented ways. The Covid-19 period strongly intensified the disillusionment and mistrust felt by this section of the society. This has been critical in shaping their perceptions of the ensuing crises - the war in Ukraine and its associated economic impacts.

The main concerns expressed by the conservative participants are characterised by a set of strongly nativist discourses. Their primary critique is, that in the light of the war-fuelled energy crisis and the staggering inflation, the new right-wing government was not doing enough to protect its citizens from falling into poverty. The people we interviewed were angered by the government's empty phrases about the need to be solidary and thought that the financial resources channelled into the support of Ukraine ought to be first distributed among the Czech population. There was a prevalent perception among this group that the Czech population was being deprived of their basic living standards at the expense of the government's help for Ukraine and this, according to them, was wrong. In terms of their electoral choices, every single respondent of this group was strongly anti-government (SPOLU), wished for their resignation and supported one of the extreme right-wing parties such as SPD, Trikolóra or

Svobodní. This is because the extreme right-wing parties are currently at the forefront of the ongoing anti-government protests, which raise issues of energy security and poverty and see them as direct consequences of the war in Ukraine.

The second category of participants, which we labelled 'liberal' - those with (neo)liberal values, which tend to be pro-Western oriented, economically secure and pro-government - saw the war in Ukraine as 'their war'. Participants from this category were strongly pro-government and in the last parliamentary elections voted for either of the currently governing coalitions (SPOLU or PirSTAN). Many of them expressed a genuine satisfaction with the change in political power - namely the stepping down of Andrej Babiš as prime minister, who they perceived as morally corrupt and 'populist', and therefore unfit to govern. The liberal participants fully condemned Russia's invasion of Ukraine and felt proud that the Czech government took such a generous stance in aiding Ukraine in the conflict. Moreover, they acknowledged the difficult position of the fairly new government in dealing with the consequences of multiple crises (Covid-19, energy, inflation, war) and thought that the wide critique of them was unjust.

The final group, labelled 'progressive' - a group consisting of the youngest participants of the sample, who hold strong progressive values and believe that more state-interventionist policies are necessary - also strongly condemned the war. Majority of the individuals I spoke to were active in delivering refugee aid and stood by a belief that anyone escaping an armed conflict has a right for safe passage and asylum. Contrary to the liberal participants, representatives of this group were fairly critical of the government. They particularly emphasised the hypocrisy of some of the political representatives which during the 2015 refugee crisis were not willing to take in any refugees and today proclaimed the importance of solidarity with people fleeing the war. On a domestic level, the participants thought that the government's excessively neoliberal approach to the economy and 'asocial' social politics were going to cause further social discontent. They also raised concerns with the growing influence of the conservative sections of the government, especially with regards to the LGBTQ+ and women's reproductive rights. Overall, the progressively leaning respondents were either voting for the centrist Pirate Party or felt widely disillusioned because of the lack of available progressive left-wing parties.

5. Conclusions

There are intriguing similarities and differences between the two case studies, the basic results of which are reported here. The two key similarities are: expedient transformation of the initial shock caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine into massive mobilisation of large numbers of people ready to help the swelling tide of refugees and the powerful refraction of the event's framing through cultural prisms focused on ideological positions (Czechia) or the reshuffling of collective memory (Poland).

A simple idea organised our initial research design: let's collect people's narrative constructions of the invasion and the massive wave of refugees. And let's try to identify the main features of three main types of such constructions: conservative, liberal, and progressive. While the Czech sample was composed of the representatives of all three options and thus

easily conformed to our initial scheme, the Polish respondents proved to be more “complex” and we did not manage to sort them out into the three preconceived ideological slots. We do not know whether this is the result of our non-random and perhaps idiosyncratic sample or a reflection of an important feature of Polish society. It is possible that ideological framing does not work very well when it comes to the Polish-Ukrainian relationships. The history is complex and rendered in multiple, often contradictory, narratives that do not line up easily with crisply delineated ideological positions.

Our study suggests that the Czech response both to the Russian invasion and the wave of refugees was heavily coloured by the respondents' prior ideological orientations. The respondents we branded “conservative” tended to think that the Czech Republic should stay out of the “conflict” and to worry about the negative impact of the large number of refugees on the Czech economy. The “liberals” in our sample, true to their creed's legalistic bent, were enraged by Russia's egregious violation of international law and saw the refugees as an asset for the economy. While there is very little to be argued against the virtues of altruism and solidarity, the findings of our research shows that these seemingly universal principles have, even in the case of the liberal participants, their limitations. Namely, solidarity can only be unconditionally extended to those who are culturally similar to us, able to assimilate or who can provide a source of capital for the national economy. This reservation, often only thinly suggested, was criticised by most progressive participants during our interviews.

By and large, the picture of the situation presented by the “progressives” was similar to the one offered by the “liberals,” although they often complained that Ukrainians received an incomparably warmer welcome than the earlier waves of refugees from North Africa or the Middle East. Importantly, we noted liberal hesitation and equivocation in this matter. Even they shared the view that people the country was about to accept without preconditions should not be too culturally different from the host population. At least some liberal respondents seem to have been saying that there need to exist some cultural boundaries imposed on the Czech solidarity with the suffering Czechs' readiness to help.

As we have already signalled, it was not possible to sort out ideologically the Polish respondents' responses to the situation. What has become clear, however, was the powerful impact of various, often competing, narratives in the complex memory field around the Polish-Ukrainian relations. It is the relationship steeped in history that is often related in heavily ideologized stories. We have noted, however, that under the impact of the invasion and the tragic fate of millions of Ukrainian refugees, the “friendly” narrative on the relationship between the two nations came to the fore. The far right populist forces, such as *Konfederacja*, that had used to propose narratives designed to exacerbate anti-Ukrainian sentiments as a matter of routine, discovered that the popular resonance of such narratives declined.

Right-wing populists are not satisfied with cultivating an image of a powerful, alien “elite” that is vertically juxtaposed to the “people” and needs to be resisted if not brought down; they always look for horizontal enemies, whose image can be used to set up boundaries between “proper” and “improper” people. Given the complex history of the Polish-Ukrainian relations and the existence of a powerful narrative that frames this relationship in terms of conflict and hatred, Ukrainians are a convenient potential antagonist of a narrative establishing “pure Polishness.” Given this situation in the discursive field, the Law and Justice Party (PiS) that ruled the country since 2015 to 2023 (the time of this writing), cultivated a politically expedient

ambiguity, trying to maintain good relationships with Ukraine, but, at the same time, rehabilitating or simply commemorating historical figures and events that denote negative and controversial aspects of the Polish-Ukrainian historical entanglements. Polish reaction might have a lot to do with the previous history of Ukrainian labour migration to Poland. Ukrainians' contribution to the Polish economy had been substantial before 2022 (Wodzicki *et al* 2022) and they had been perceived as “better” labour immigrants than those coming from Africa, Middle East or Asia, particularly Muslims (Bartłomiejski and Kowalewska 2021).

When the war broke out, the ruling party started promoting a different master narrative, in which the great Polish nation is Ukraine's number one ally. It was designed to appeal to its nationalist voting base, always keen on having its national pride reinforced and to build up Poland's international position, globally and within the EU. The enemy was Russia, of course, though the relationship between PiS and Russia remained ambiguous, with the partially state-owned Polish refinery, *Orlen*, still buying Russian oil, while the government insisted on further sanctions and military support to Ukraine.⁹ While redefining Ukrainians as friends, PiS had to revise the set of chief antagonists in the nationalist narrative it promoted. Other refugees, often from Africa and the Middle East, were assigned that role, which made it easier to direct negative emotions towards ethnic and racial others, rather than Ukrainians seen as fellow Slavs (Babińska, *et al* 2022:56). This has reinforced the racist tone of the Polish right-wing populist discourse (Pacewicz 2023a).

Related to this redefinition of “the Ukrainian” in the Polish discursive field and related strengthening of the positive image of Ukrainians among the population at large, was an unanticipated fracture on the right-side of the Polish political spectrum. Since coming to power in 2015, the ruling party's ideology started drifting right, apparently out of fear of being outflanked by far right groups. Far-right organisations in Poland, including political parties, are largely anti-Ukrainian, and although their narratives belong to the political fringe, anti-Ukraininess was also present in the discourse of the ruling PiS. However, in 2021, this party reframed its discourse on Ukrainians to stay in tune with a strongly pro-Ukrainian popular sentiment. As a result far-right activists, politicians, and public intellectuals got marginalised by the government that had on numerous occasions cooperated with them before and supported their work financially.

The war, a total event that united the nation, literally and discursively, became also a burden for Polish society, which started to feel the economic crisis really strongly. The inflation became a major issue, though it did not change attitudes towards Ukrainian refugees as much as it did in Czechia. Importantly, although our respondents were critical of the government for its slow response to the crisis and its hypocrisy, the most recent survey showed that 80,4% of respondents assessed the government's actions regarding the Ukrainian crisis positively (32,5% - decisively positively and 47,9% - positively).¹⁰ In January 2023, 82% of Poles were supportive of the idea that the member state of the EU and NATO should support Ukraine until its final victory over Russia. This is in huge contrast to Germany, where only 42% of respondents expressed such support (Glowacki 2023).

⁹ <https://notesfrompoland.com/2023/02/10/poland-still-getting-10-of-oil-from-russia-admits-minister-blaming-lack-of-eu-embargo/>

¹⁰ <https://wiadomosci.wp.pl/to-jest-nokaut-tak-polacy-oceniaja-dzialania-rzadu-pis-ws-pomocy-dla-ukrainy-6867614526896768a>. Accessed: 5 March 2023.

We close the study with a cautious generalisation. While the Czech reaction to the Russian invasion of Ukraine and the resulting wave of refugees was framed through the prism of people's ideological positions and their worries about the potential negative impact of immigrants on the Czech economy and its labour market, the Polish reaction was not so clearly influenced by people's ideological views. It was, however, entwined with the events-induced reconsideration of the historically evolved cultural pattern dictating mutual attitudes and relations. That pattern, deeply rooted in a long and complex history of conflict or cooperation, needs to be understood in the context of an extensive and conflicted field of historical narratives that are impossible to ignore by either side, particularly when Poles and Ukrainians react to contemporary events that impact them both. If there is a way to render this conclusion in one sentence, here it is: while Czechs reacted pragmatically and/or through the prism of political ideology, the Polish reaction was inescapably filtered through the prism of thickly emplotted and conflicted albeit evolving historical memory.

Figures and tables

Figure 1: Photo of Polish volunteers helping Ukrainians in the first days after war escalation, TVN24.pl, 27 February 2022, © TVN24.

Figure 2: Photo of a solidarity demonstration with Ukraine, Prague - Vaclavske Namesti, February 24 2022 © Zewlakk.

Figure 3: Photo of an anti-government demonstration, Prague Vaclavske Namesti, September 3, 2022, © Kamaryt Michal.

Table 1: Polish participants in the study.

Table 2: Czech participants in the study.

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